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IDENTIFICATION OF POTENTIAL TERRITORIAL AND REGIONAL OPPORTUNITIES

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The Centre for Studies and Expertise on Risks, the Environment, Mobility and Urban Planning (Cerema), a public administrative body operating under the French Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion; the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), an organisation with an international legal personality; and the National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), a French public scientific and technological institution, are beneficiaries of the FCCIS project, which is co-funded by the European Commission. This document is a project deliverable produced by these three entities. The studies and technical considerations presented in it do not constitute an agreement or commitment by a CERN Member State or the European Union for the expansion of the existing research facilities at CERN and the operation thereof.

GLOSSARY:

All of the abbreviations used in this document are available and updated in the online glossary:

<https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/FCC/GlossaryOfTerms>.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. FUTURE CIRCULAR COLLIDER STUDY

The aim of the Future Circular Collider (FCC) Feasibility Study is to develop a concept for a new research infrastructure to host the next generation of higher-performance particle colliders in order to extend the research currently being conducted at CERN once the research programme of the High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) comes to an end in around 2040.

The goal of the FCC programme is to push back the energy and intensity frontiers of particle beams in the search for new physics. The programme provides for the installation of two particle colliders, which would be operated successively in a new underground facility with a circumference of approximately 91 km. The scientific research programme associated with these two machines would last until the end of the 21st century. The working hypothesis is based on a first operation phase with an electron–positron collider (FCC-ee) lasting until 2057, followed by a second phase with a hadron collider (FCC-hh). An international collaboration of over 150 universities, research institutes and industrial partners from all over the world is developing the concepts for the two circular colliders, the new experiment detectors to be installed at the collision points and the technical infrastructure required to operate the facility, as well as producing cost estimates, global implementation scenarios and appropriate governance structures.

The underground infrastructure would be located in an area straddling the French-Swiss border. The tunnel would pass under Lake Geneva and the Arve and Rhône rivers. The report on the constraints and opportunities associated with the site¹ (Gutleber, et al., 2024) is based on eight access sites, spaced at regular intervals, for the construction work, the installation of equipment and the supply of the necessary technical systems, each site having a surface area of between 4 and 6 ha. There would be one technical site² in Switzerland, one technical site and one scientific site³ in the Department of Ain, in France, and five sites (three scientific sites and two technical sites) in the Department of Haute-Savoie, in France (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). The main CERN site in Meyrin (Switzerland) would continue to operate. The CERN site in Prévessin (France) would also remain in operation and would be used to operate the injector complex for the FCC.

¹ J. Gutleber et al (2024), *Synthèse des contraintes et opportunités d'implantation du FCC*, <https://zenodo.org/record/7614421>

² Technical site: site dedicated to the technical facilities required to ensure the smooth operation of the machine
Scientific site: site dedicated to the experiments

³ Next to the existing CERN sites

Figure 1: Overview of site placement in the region, based on the current working hypothesis, showing the communes and intercommunal areas affected, either directly or indirectly, in France (Departments of Ain and Haute-Savoie) and in Switzerland (Canton of Geneva). Source: CERN.

The planned surface sites for the technical facilities have been optimised in accordance with the "Avoid-Reduce-Offset" principle ("*Éviter-réduire-compenser*" from the French Environmental Code, article R122-5⁴), taking into account the constraints related to the design of the particle collider, the territorial issues identified at this stage, particularly regarding urbanism, nature and agriculture, and many other elements, in order to limit the impact of the project while ensuring the creation of a world-class scientific facility. The Avoid-Reduce-Offset approach was adopted in order to strike a balance between scientific excellence, territorial compatibility and management of the risks associated with the project's implementation.

⁴ https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/article_lc/LEGIARTI000043743342

1.2. MOTIVATIONS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE PRESENT DOCUMENT

When designing a new research infrastructure using large-scale circular particle colliders, located in a border region comprising both urban and rural areas, it is necessary to reflect on the local synergies and opportunities that could arise. This is all the more important in the FCC project, since a large part of the infrastructure would be located in an entirely new zone (in the Department of Haute-Savoie in France, where no CERN facilities currently exist). Beyond its contribution to scientific knowledge, the infrastructure must be integrated seamlessly into the environment and be welcomed by the local population. Figure 2 shows the current CERN presence in the region, with the LHC and the CERN campuses, as well as the placement of the FCC project.

Figure 2: Map showing the existing CERN infrastructure and the FCC project. Source: CERN.

The study was driven by the following factors:

- The considerable **geographical scope** of the research infrastructure, of which a large part will be in an area where no CERN facilities currently exist (Haute-Savoie).
- The **limitations** in terms of **road and rail infrastructure**.
- The **border** between the two countries, one of which is not a member of the European Union.
- The **number of people contributing** to the scientific programme, across various installations.
- Societal developments with respect to **mobility**.
- Societal developments with respect to **work and lifestyle habits**.
- **Balanced regional** integration.
- **Regional development**.
- **Development of tourism**.

- **Socio-economic impact.**
- **Demographic development.**
- **Economic development in the region in general.**

This document aims to provide a preliminary summary of the potential benefits and synergies at the local level (communes in the vicinity of the FCC), the territorial level (Departments of Ain and Haute-Savoie and the Canton of Geneva) and the regional level (Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region and the Canton of Vaud). Although synergies have been discussed and studied together with regional stakeholders, they remain at the stage of hypotheses and must continue to be explored as the study progresses, in collaboration with local stakeholders. The support and engagement of the Host States will be decisive for the implementation of these synergies, since these territorial developments go beyond the scope of the research infrastructure. This document may therefore serve as a starting point.

The identification of some of these potential synergies has been made possible thanks to the cooperation of numerous stakeholders, notably, the Prefecture of the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes Region, the Prefecture of the Department of Haute-Savoie, the Haute-Savoie Departmental Council, Greater Annecy, the *Pôle métropolitain du Genevois français* (grouping of French local authorities in the areas bordering the Canton of Geneva), the municipalities affected by the FCC, including Vulbens, Digny-en-Vuache, Challex, Ferney-Voltaire, Presinge, Choulex, Nangy, Contamine-sur-Arve, Eteaux, La Roche-sur-Foron, Groisy, Charvonnex, Cercier and Marlioz, SYANE (Haute-Savoie union for energy and digital services), ADEME (French Agency for Ecological Transition), SIG (Geneva utility company), OCEN (Geneva Cantonal Office for Energy), OCBA (Geneva Cantonal Office for Buildings), Ginger Burgeap, Lactalis Group, SNCF (French national railway company), *Syndicat des Eaux des Rocailles et de Bellecombe* (French water company), RTE (French electricity transmission system operator), ENEDIS (French electricity distributor), DREAL (Regional Directorate for Environment, Development and Housing) and DDT de la Haute-Savoie (Haute-Savoie Departmental Directorate for Land Use). **This list does not include all the stakeholders who have had discussions with various members of the FCC teams.**

This document was written in parallel with the document *Analyse des besoins et des options pour un pôle FCC supplémentaire* (L. Alix, 2024). It is also linked to the overall socioeconomic analysis of the FCC project being carried out by the *Centre for Industrial Studies* (CSIL) (E. Sirtori et al., 2024) and is based on the six pillars of that study (see Figure 3: The six socio-economic impact areas of the FCC project and their application at the territorial level.), namely, scientific output, education and training, industrial benefits, IT benefits, cultural impact and value as a public good. These six socioeconomic impact areas can be applied at both the territorial and the regional level. Public services and territorial development – an impact area that relates solely to the local area – can also be added to the list.

Figure 3: The six socio-economic impact areas of the FCC project and their application at the territorial level. Source: Cerema.

The synergies described in this document are based on these themes. For ease of understanding, they have been grouped into two categories: those arising as a result of the needs of the FCC infrastructure and those arising as a result of the presence of the FCC in the region.

The potential benefits associated with the needs of the FCC infrastructure will be outlined in chapter 4. These are:

- Recovery of waste heat from the FCC.
- Re-use and redistribution of water.
- Reinforcement of the electricity network.
- Potential re-use of the LHC tunnel.

These aspects have an impact at the local and the territorial level.

The potential benefits associated with the presence of the FCC infrastructure in the region will be presented in chapter 5. These are:

- The creation of sustainable scientific tourism.
- The development of local services.
- The enhancement of transport options.
- The promotion of education and training.
- Collaboration with emergency services.
- Links with companies.
- Other possible synergies: compensatory agricultural measures, sharing of digital infrastructures, sharing of data concerning the territory.

All of these aspects have a local, territorial and regional influence, with the exception of local services and transport, which are more local and territorial in their scope.

2. BACKGROUND INFORMATION

2.1. PROJECT PHASES

The construction, installation, commissioning, operation, maintenance and continuous upgrading of a particle collider require a technical, scientific and technological facility that is tailored to the project, as well as various activities carried out by multidisciplinary personnel. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a timeline for these different phases for the first phase of the FCC project, the FCC-ee. The FCC-hh will begin operation later, towards the end of the century.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35
Conception										Exploitation																								
Construction et installation										Z	W	H	Amélioration	TT																				

Figure 4: Timeline of the different phases of the FCC-ee in years. Source: Author.

This study will focus on the construction phase (beginning between 2030 and 2035) and the operation phase (beginning between 2040 and 2045).

2.2. SURFACE SITES

Eight surface sites are envisaged for the project: four scientific sites, where the particle beams collide in the detectors that are used for scientific research, and four technical sites for the installation of and access to the technical systems of the collider. The locations of these sites are shown below (see **Error! Reference source not found.**: the circles in the image show the location only and are not indicative of the surface area of the sites).

- PA – scientific site – Ferney-Voltaire (France, Department of Ain)
- PB – technical site – Presinge/Choulex (Switzerland, Canton of Geneva)
- PD – scientific site – Nangy (France, Department of Haute-Savoie)
- PF – technical site – Etaux/La-Roche-sur-Foron (France, Department of Haute-Savoie)
- PG – scientific site – Charvonnex/Groisy (France, Department of Haute-Savoie)
- PH – technical site – Cercier/Marlioz (France, Department of Haute-Savoie)
- PJ – scientific site – Vulbens/Dingy-en-Vuache (France, Department of Haute-Savoie)
- PL – technical site – Challex (France, Department of Ain)

Figure 5: Location and distribution of the scientific and technical sites. The circles in the image show the location only and are not indicative of the surface area of the sites. Source: Author.

2.3. NUMBER OF PEOPLE PRESENT ON EACH SITE

The number of persons present on each site per day will depend on the project phase. As a guide, Table 1 shows the figures based on the operation of the LHC. The operating model of the FCC has not yet been defined; it is therefore not possible to show the exact number of people who will be associated with the FCC, although the figures may be similar to those for the LHC. At the moment, it is only possible to make assumptions based on the figures from the LHC programme.

Table 1: Number of people present on each site for the different phases.

	Construction	Installation	Operation	Annual maintenance	Long shutdown for maintenance
Period	10 years	5 years (partly covering the construction phase)	8 months per year	4 months per year	1 year, once only during the entire duration of the programme
Personnel per scientific site	40 to 300 workers	200 to 300 technicians	4 to 8 team members 12 to 16 technicians	100 technicians	200 to 300 technicians
Personnel per technical site	20 to 130 workers	100 technicians	0 to 9 technicians	15 to 30 technicians	100 technicians

3. PROJECT PARTICIPANTS AND ECONOMIC IMPACT

3.1. ECONOMIC IMPACT PRODUCED BY THOSE PARTICIPATING IN THE FCC

CERN is home to the world's largest particle accelerator complex. This platform for research in fundamental science, with its versatile particle accelerators working with a plethora of different particle beams at different intensities and energies, continues to attract scientists and engineers from all over the world. While a large part of the scientific analysis is carried out by the researchers at their home institutes, scientists and engineers involved in the research programmes spend significant amounts of time at CERN, both to advance the scientific capabilities of the infrastructures and to explore the possibilities that this infrastructure offers them. The presence of these people has multiple economic repercussions, notably in terms of consumer spending in the region⁵.

Today, over 16 000 people are involved in CERN's research programmes, of whom approximately 14 000 are permanently active. According to the personnel statistics⁶, 24% of those involved are aged 30 or under, 34% are between the ages of 31 and 45, 28% are between the ages of 46 and 60 and 14% are aged 61 or over. Not all of these people reside in the local area.

Today, approximately 8800 of the people participating in CERN's research programmes are considered as residents of France and Switzerland, with the majority living in the Departments of Haute-Savoie and Ain and in the Canton of Geneva. 63% live in France and 37% live in Switzerland (see **Error! Reference source not found.****Error! Reference source not found.**).

⁵ L. Alix et J. Gutleber (2023), *La contribution du FCC à l'économie locale : la valeur des dépenses de consommation, CNRS et CERN*, <https://zenodo.org/records/7565580>

⁶ CERN (2021), *CERN Personnel Statistics*, <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2809746/files/CERN-HR-STAFF-STAT-2021-RESTR.pdf>

Distribution of people working at CERN

07/07/2023 FCC-230701655- PLA_CERN_personnel_distribution_V0001

Figure 6 Place of residence of people currently working at CERN. Source: CERN.

According to the report on the contribution of the FCC to the local economy⁷, the number of active CERN personnel living in the region will remain stable during the operating phase of the FCC-ee. However, the geographical distribution is likely to evolve slightly, with 75% residing in France and 25% in Switzerland. This is owing to the infrastructure that will need to be installed in Haute-Savoie. Compared to today, activities in Haute-Savoie will be distributed over a wider geographical area, with five surface sites, including three scientific sites.

The presence of these people will have an economic impact in terms of consumer spending at local level, estimated at approximately 3.4 billion euros over 30 years or around 113 million euros per year. If the FCC project does not go ahead, this figure could be considered as a potential loss for the regional economy. Approximately 70% of spending by the people working on the FCC project would be in France and 30% in Switzerland (see Figure 7). This estimate includes the construction phase, in which fewer CERN personnel will be residing in the area. By comparison, in its operation phase, the LHC programme generates an economic impact of around 8.9 billion euros in consumer spending over an equivalent 30-year period. This gives an idea of how the regional economic impact of the project may develop beyond the initial phase of the FCC. This spending will support the creation of jobs in the Departments of Haute-Savoie and Ain and in the Cantons of Geneva and Vaud, as presented in section 3.2.

⁷ L. Alix et J. Gutleber (2023), *La contribution du FCC à l'économie locale : la valeur des dépenses de consommation*, CNRS et CERN, <https://zenodo.org/records/7565580>

Figure 7: Household expenditure generated by CERN during the 30-year FCC-ee phase in France and Switzerland. Source: CNRS and CERN.

3.2. IMPACT ON EMPLOYMENT

The study of the impact of the FCC on value added and on employment⁸ shows that the construction costs, capital expenditure, consumer spending and operational expenditure associated with the infrastructure will have an impact on employment both globally and nationally within the two Host States. The average number of jobs created or filled per year can be broken down as follows:

- 6000 jobs directly linked to the project in the fields of science, engineering, administration and the management of the sites in France and Switzerland.
- 8500 jobs indirectly linked to or created by the presence of these activities
 - o including 3800 jobs in France and 1000 in Switzerland.
- 3400 jobs linked to spending related to the operation of the research infrastructure in the region
 - o including 200 jobs in France and 100 in Switzerland.
- 2800 jobs linked to tourism from visitors to CERN
 - o including 1000 jobs in France and 700 in Switzerland.
- 11 500 jobs linked to construction expenditure for the FCC
 - o including 1200 jobs in France and 200 in Switzerland.
- 1200 jobs in the sectors dealing with the supply of the resources needed to operate the infrastructure, notably including energy from green sources
 - o including 800 jobs in Europe.

⁸ G. Streicher (2023), *Building CERN's Future Circular Collider. An Estimation of its Impact on Value Added and Employment*, WIFO, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7382706>

Thus, approximately 14 500 jobs on average per year would be created in the Host States, France and Switzerland, as a result of the FCC-ee programme, of which at least 2200 jobs would be in the Departments of Ain and Haute-Savoie and in the Canton of Geneva.

According to the same study, the following sectors would derive direct benefits from the project:

- Construction.
- Industry in general.
- Materials and product manufacturing.
- Machine and electrical equipment manufacturing.
- Wholesale and retail.
- Transport and storage.
- Professional, scientific and technical services.
- Administrative and support services.
- Tourism and associated services.

4. POTENTIAL OPPORTUNITIES AND SYNERGIES LINKED TO THE NEEDS OF THE FCC INFRASTRUCTURE

4.1. WASTE HEAT RECOVERY

4.1.1. Context

The FCC cooling system will use non-potable water to cool several subsystems⁹ of the particle accelerator, the experiments and the technical infrastructure. This water, circulating in closed circuits, will absorb the heat and dissipate it in cooling towers, where some of the hot water will evaporate. The water will enter the cooling system at approximately 20 °C and exit at around 40 to 70 °C, depending on the system being cooled. It is possible to recover this heat for use in urban networks, for example for heating systems in homes, the service sector and even industry. Table 2 shows the estimated amount of heat available per year for each site, and Table 3 shows the tentative timescales for the FCC-ee operating modes¹⁰.

Table 2: Amount of heat available per year per site (in GWh).

Site/Mode	Z	W	H	Long shutdown	tt
PA	138	152	172	16	225
PB	15	18	23	0	34
PD	138	152	172	16	225
PF	15	18	23	0	34
PG	138	152	172	16	225
PH	230	314	336	3	524
PJ	138	152	172	16	225
PL	25	48	56	1	109
Total per year	836	1005	1128	68	1603

⁹ The magnets, power converters, radiofrequency amplifiers, cryogenic refrigeration equipment, ventilation systems, etc.

¹⁰ During the operation of the FCC-ee, four operating modes are planned, each with increasing beam energy. These different modes enable specific particles to be targeted.

Table 3: FCC-ee operating modes and period.

Mode	Beam energy	Tentative period ¹¹	Number of years
Z	45.6 GeV	2045–2048	4
W	80 GeV	2049–2050	2
H	120 GeV	2051–2053	3
Long shutdown		2054	1
tt	182.5 GeV	2055–2059	5

Since the amount of heat fluctuates from week to week, the GWh shown are cumulative over the year.

A technical and economic study of heat recovery is under way in collaboration with an industrial partner. The methodology followed is outlined in part I of the report produced by this partner¹².

This study has three phases:

- Part I: Evaluation of the potential heat consumption (list of consumers).
- Part II: Evaluation of the waste heat recovery process and how to improve it (improvement of part 1 by accounting for seasonality, energy density, distance and storage requirements to obtain a net potential).
- Part III: Evaluation of the integration of complementary technologies (heat storage, potential temperature increase and effects, technical-economic analysis).

The following section outlines the main opportunities (non-exhaustive list). **It presents the current heat consumption of the territory and the gross potential for heat recovery, corresponding to part I of the study. This does not mean that the amount of heat recovered and reused will be the same as the amount indicated; the net potential will need to be evaluated in the next two phases of the study.**

4.1.2. Gross heat consumption potential by site

4.1.2.1. Site PA – Ferney-Voltaire, France

A heat recovery network is being developed at Point 8 of the LHC (LHCb experiment) in Ferney-Voltaire (see annex 8.1). It will enable 44 GWh of heat to be provided to the commune of Ferney-Voltaire and the new urban development zone (ZAC, in French) known as “Ferney-Genève Innovation”. Since site PA of the FCC will be located close by, it could replace Point 8 of the LHC for the heat supply. If this is the case, there are many possibilities for the reuse of the recovered heat. Table 4 shows the annual gross heat recovery potential.

Table 4: Annual gross heat consumption potential at site PA in France and in Switzerland.

5-km radius	10-km radius	Heat available
1678 GWh	3651 GWh	138–225 GWh

Box 1: Discussions with Services Industriels de Genève (Geneva utilities company)

Talks are under way with SIG concerning its capacity to recover and use heat from the FCC in the local area, for example, by connecting the FCC network to its own networks (GeniTerre and GeniLac).

¹¹ The exact period will depend on when the FCC operation phase begins.

¹² A. Guiavarch (2024), *Étude de valorisation de la chaleur disponible du FCC, Partie I : Étude du potentiel de consommation*, Ginger Burgeap, FCC-2401300900-BURGEAP

4.1.2.2. Site PB – Presinge/Choulex, Switzerland

Since this site is located in Switzerland, SIG is currently investigating its capacity to recover and use heat from the FCC. There are several potential consumers nearby (Centre de Lullier, prison, hospital). The commissioned research firm has estimated the potential gross consumption in Switzerland and in France. Table 5 shows the gross heat recovery potential.

Table 5: Annual gross heat consumption potential at site PB.

5-km radius	Heat available
657 GWh in Switzerland and France	15–34 GWh

4.1.2.3. Site PD – Nangy, France

There are several possibilities for this site. The main ones are the Centre Hospitalier Alpes Léman (CHAL), located 400 m away from site PD, the Fromagerie de la Tournette, located 600 m away, and the Bellecombe/Scientrier waste-water treatment plant, just over 2 km away. Table 6 shows the gross heat recovery potential at site PD.

Table 6: Annual gross heat consumption potential at site PD.

5-km radius	Heat available
49 GWh	138–225 GWh

Box 2: Discussions with Fromagerie de la Tournette and Syndicat des Eaux des Rocailles et de Bellecombe (French water company)

The discussions with *Fromagerie de la Tournette* (Lactalis Group) have confirmed the company's interest in obtaining a share of the heat energy recovered from the FCC. Its annual requirements amount to around 6 GWh, with temperatures ranging from 35 to 90°C. Manufacturing and tank cleaning are the most energy-intensive activities. The cheese factory also requires cold temperatures for the storage and ripening of cheeses. Cheese production at the factory will be expanded in the coming years, further justifying the use of available heat from the FCC. The desire to transition to renewable energy sources may facilitate the reuse of heat from the FCC. This is part of a broader effort to reuse resources. For example, a decree¹³ was recently issued on the reuse of water in the food sector.

Lactalis Group owns this cheese factory, as well as the one at Eteaux (near site PF), where production is on a larger scale.

Discussions are also under way with the water authority *Syndicat des Eaux des Rocailles et de Bellecombe* concerning the waste-water treatment plant at Bellecombe/Scientrier. The authority is interested in using recovered heat for biogas production, which would require a temperature of 37 °C, and possibly for drying greenhouses. The waste-water treatment plant's anaerobic digestion unit is described in annex 8.2.

¹³ <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/jorf/id/JORFTEXT000049010414>

4.1.2.4. Site PF – Eteaux/La Roche-sur-Foron, France

This site presents several possibilities, the main ones being the *Société fromagère d'Eteaux*, a member of Lactalis Group (2 km), and the commune of Roche-sur-Foron as a whole. Table 7 shows the gross heat recovery potential.

Table 7: Annual gross heat consumption potential at site PF.

5-km radius	10-km radius	Heat available
59 GWh	126 GWh	15–34 GWh

Box 3: Discussions with Société fromagère d'Eteaux.

This cheese factory also belongs to the Lactalis Group. The discussions with *Société fromagère d'Eteaux* have also confirmed the company's interest in using waste heat recovered from the FCC. Its annual requirements amount to around 10 GWh. The temperatures required range from around 35 °C to around 90 °C.

4.1.2.5. Site PG – Charvonnex/Groisy, France

Opportunities are more limited in Groisy and Charvonnex, and areas with potential are not grouped together. Nevertheless, the commune of Groisy is developing, and new activities could be undertaken there in connection with site PG (see

Box 7: Discussions with the representatives of the communes of Groisy and Charvonnex.). These activities could be directly linked to the FCC network, thereby justifying the creation of such a network in the commune of Groisy. The commune of Argonay and part of the city of Annecy, both located within a 10-km radius of Groisy, may also present opportunities for the reuse of waste heat from the FCC. Table 8 shows the gross heat recovery potential.

Table 8: Annual gross heat consumption potential at site PG.

5-km radius	10-km radius	Heat available
49 GWh	907 GWh	138–225 GWh

4.1.2.6. Site PH – Cercier/Marlioz, France

This location is the most complex of the sites, with few major consumers located within a 5-km radius. However, it has the greatest capacity for heat production, owing to the radiofrequency systems. The commune of Balme-de-Sillingy is located just within the 5-km radius (see Table 9), and a new activity could be planned here (see section 4.1.4.). This situation opens the possibility of developing, together with academic and industrial partners, a technology that would enable heat from the cooling system to be distributed to more distant areas. In response to this particular situation, an R&D project is being defined and will be launched soon.

Table 9: Annual gross heat consumption potential at site PH.

5-km radius	Heat available
15 GWh	230–524 GWh

4.1.2.7. Site PJ – Dingy-en-Vuache/Vulbens, France

The 5-km perimeter includes the Grands Chavannoux business park, which is currently undergoing development (new high school, new police station, expansion of existing premises). The area could be expanded in conjunction with the PJ scientific site, and the new activities there could benefit from the available heat (see

Box 8: Discussions with the representatives of the communes of Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens.). Table 10 shows the gross heat recovery potential.

Table 10: Annual gross heat consumption potential at site PJ.

5-km radius	10-km radius	Heat available
21 GWh	109 GWh	138–225 GWh

4.1.2.8. Site PL – Challex, France

Some areas of interest exist around site PL in France and Switzerland. Table 11 shows the gross heat recovery potential.

Table 11: Annual gross heat consumption potential at site PL.

5-km radius	Heat available
34 GWh	25–109 GWh

Box 4: Visit to the Ferme Aquaponique du Pays de Gex (aquaponic farm)

The possibility of a new aquaponic farm has been raised during meetings with representatives of the commune of Challex. A visit to the *Ferme Aquaponique du Pays de Gex* in Versonnex was organised in order to understand the running and needs of the farm. The principle behind this type of farming is explained in annex 8.3. The heat requirements vary depending on the food grown and the fish used. Generally, the temperature ranges between 18 and 28 °C and consumption is around 0.5 GWh per year for a 2000 m² farm.

4.1.3. Heat supply potential according to different variables

The previous section presented the region's heat consumption. This section looks at how to increase the potential for recovering waste heat. Various variables can influence this potential: adapting the infrastructure's operating schedule according to the time of year when it is most needed, redistributing the heat between sites to meet higher demand in some places and lower demand in others, and/or extending the perimeter of the areas covered beyond 5 km.

Table 12 shows the potential heat recovery under different scenarios:

- 5 km perimeter and operation not adapted according to schedule.
- 5 km perimeter and operation adapted according to the schedule (period when demand for heat is highest).
- 5 km perimeter and operation adapted according to the schedule and redistribution of the heat to the sites with the highest demand (e.g. PL to PA).

Table 12 : Value creation for heat supply under different scenarios.

	Minimum heat supply scenario [GWh] (5 km area + non-adapted operation schedule)					Value creation rate [%]				
	Z	W	H	L.S.	tt	Z	W	H	L.S	tt
Total	223	239	256	60	296	27%	24%	23%	88%	18%
	Conservative scenario [GWh] (5 km area + operation schedule adaptation)					Value creation rate [%]				
	Z	W	H	L.S	tt	Z	W	H	L.S	tt
Total	308	339	371	60	441	37%	34%	33%	88%	28%
	Optimistic heat supply scenario [GWh] (5 km area + operation schedule adaptation + heat distribution)					Value creation rate [%]				
	Z	W	H	L.S.	tt	Z	W	H	L.S	tt
Total	414	471	529	68	710	49%	47%	47%	100%	44%

4.1.4. Benefits

The provision of heat generates benefits in four areas:

- 1) **Increased purchasing power of the population:** the organisation operating the FCC does not aim to profit economically from the infrastructure. Energy can thus be provided by network operators at very competitive prices. According to the French Multi-Annual Energy Plan (*programmation pluriannuelle de l'énergie* (PPE))¹⁴, waste-to-energy plants sell recovered heat at very competitive prices of between 10 and 25 €/MWh. Waste heat recovery may therefore be the preferred energy choice for heating, hot water and cooling. The price of waste heat from CERN facilities supplied through the Ferney-Voltaire heat recovery network will be even lower. According to the study by AMORCE and ADEME, the average sales price for networks supplied mainly by renewable and recovered energy sources was 78.2 €/MWh (including taxes) in 2020¹⁵. The research firm Ginger Burgeap found more recent average prices to be in the same ballpark. Based on this model, the savings potential is currently estimated at 50 €/MWh¹⁶ compared with gas heating and 140 €/MWh¹⁷ compared with electric heating, based on energy prices at 1 November 2023.
- 2) **Reduction of the carbon footprint linked to the electricity supply:** the estimated electricity consumption for the FCC (based on the partial use of electricity from renewable sources) equates to an average annual carbon footprint of approximately 40 000 teqCO². By supplying approximately 320 GWh of energy per year from waste heat recovery, CERN could completely offset this carbon footprint. The maximum annual heat recovery capacity is approximately 1600 GWh; therefore, as long as heat recovery systems are put in place, it should be possible to offset the carbon footprint. This issue will be examined in greater detail in the technical/economic study.
- 3) **Reduction of the carbon footprint associated with heating and cooling in the region:** the provision of energy largely from renewable sources (including waste heat) will reduce the need to use other sources of heat.
- 4) **Reduced water consumption:** heat recovery would also reduce the need for water to cool the FCC infrastructure.

¹⁴<https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/20200422%20Programmation%20pluriannuelle%20de%20l%27e%CC%81nergie.pdf>

¹⁵ AMORCE and ADEME, 2022, *Enquête sur le prix de vente de la chaleur et du froid en 2020*.

¹⁶ 50 €/MWh = 0.05 €/GWh

¹⁷ 140 €/MWh = 0.14 €/GWh

4.1.5. Other avenues for waste heat recovery

Such a large quantity of heat available at low cost is likely to give rise to new activities, including, but not limited to:

- Aquaponics (~18 to 28 °C): this cultivation method uses less water than open-field agriculture and requires heat (PL, PH, PG).
- Hydroponics (~15 to 25 °C): this cultivation method uses less water than open-field agriculture and requires heat (PL, PH, PG).
- Microalgae production using photobioreactors (~30 to 40 °C): there is currently no activity of this kind in the area.
- Shrimp farming (~27 to 31 °C): there is currently no activity of this kind in the area.
- Hot tubs and swimming pools (~25 to 37 °C): few facilities of this kind exist in the area (PA, PB, PD, PG, PJ).
- Biogas production at waste-water treatment plants (~37 to 60 °C): biogas can be produced at waste-water treatment plants using heat (for example, at the waste-water treatment plant in Bellecombe, close to site PD).
- Wood drying (~45 to 70 °C): this could be of interest to manufacturers specialising in wood (for example, in the Arve Valley).
- Sturgeon farming (~10 to 20 °C) for caviar and tropical greenhouses (~25 to 35 °C): *Tropenhaus Frutigen*, a tropical greenhouse in Frutigen, Switzerland, offers a unique concept based on fish farming, caviar production and a tropical garden. The main objective of this tropical greenhouse is to create a wide range of services based on these specialities. This has resulted in the creation of a restaurant, thematic exhibits, guided tours, spaces for events such as seminars and company meetings, and workshops. The tropical greenhouse also offers overnight accommodation and even an escape game for a fun and immersive experience¹⁸.
- Distribution of heat to the largest towns: Geneva, Annemasse and Annecy, which already have structured heat networks. A technical feasibility study will be performed to confirm whether this is possible.

An R&D collaboration with the Norwegian University of Science and Technology is currently being set up to investigate the possibility of using CO² instead of water as a heat transfer medium. This would enable heat to be transported over larger distances without significant temperature loss. This collaboration will also make it possible to study other innovative ideas for reusing this heat.

Discussions with the local authorities hosting the FCC's surface sites must be continued in order to identify potential synergies between the development of activities and the reuse of the heat emitted by the FCC facilities.

¹⁸ <https://www.tropenhaus-frutigen.ch/fr>

4.2. REUSE AND DISTRIBUTION OF WATER

4.2.1. Synergies linked to water extraction points

Cooling is essential in order to ensure the proper operation and stability of the equipment. Water is often used as a cooling agent as it can efficiently absorb heat. The following extraction points are envisaged for supply purposes (Figure 8).

- 1) The total amount of water required could be sourced from Lake Geneva via the existing water supply connection of the *Services Industriels de Genève* (SIG), which is connected to point 8 of the LHC.
- 2) As an option, a new water extraction point could be planned and built in the Arve or, depending on the technical feasibility, water could be supplied from the waste-water treatment plant in the Nangy area (see annex 8.2).
- 3) As an option, a new water extraction point could be planned and built in the Rhône, between Pougny and Vulbens.

A maximum of 650 m³/h of water will be required for approximately 170 days during the last five years of the research programme (less than three million cubic metres per year). For most of the operating period, a significantly lower volume of water will be required.

Figure 8: Water distribution with three extraction points (one existing extraction point in Switzerland and two to be built in France) as per reference scenario PA31-4.0 from September 2023. Source: CERN.

It would be feasible to source water from Lake Geneva since CERN currently obtains its water in this way, with an annual quantity greater than that mentioned on the previous page. Nevertheless, for the FCC, such a scenario would require stainless steel pipes of a large diameter and long length, and there would be an additional cost for managing the large volumes, flows and pressures around the entire circumference of the infrastructure. Building one or more new extraction points would make it possible to ensure that there is an extraction point in France and to share costs and achieve synergies with water companies (or other stakeholders) in the region. However, it is sometimes difficult to mix water from different sources, so this needs to be studied further.

Box 5: Discussions with the representatives of Haute-Savoie and certain communes.

The meetings with the authorities from the Department of Haute-Savoie and some of the communes have provided an opportunity to discuss the agricultural water shortages in the department, particularly in Vulbens, Dingy-en-Vuache and Valleiry, and to confirm their interest in having water supplied by new infrastructures.

The creation of a water extraction plant in the Rhône or the Arve would provide water for both the FCC and the local area. Depending on the water treatment method chosen for these plants, the water could be reused for agricultural, industrial or domestic purposes. The construction costs, as well as the costs of the technical and environmental studies, could be shared. It should be noted that there is a pumping station (SP2) linked to the Matailly-Moissey¹⁹ drilling project in Vulbens, in the immediate vicinity of site PJ.

In order to study this synergy at the socioeconomic level, it is necessary to quantify the volumes of water required and the possibilities for reuse in the vicinity of the Rhône and the Arve. Cross-border discussions are under way throughout the territory in order to identify needs, water usage and interconnections between water distribution networks.

For example, the two drinking water treatment plants in France (Albi and Montegut-sur-Arros) would cost between €13 000 and €15 000 per m³/h to build²⁰. A specialised study would enable a closer estimate of the cost of building a water treatment plant.

4.3. REINFORCEMENT OF THE ELECTRICITY NETWORK

A study is under way with ENEDIS (French electricity distributor), RTE (the French electricity transmission system operator) and the energy supplier *Energie et Services de Seyssel* in order to better understand the electricity needs at the sites in France and to examine the regional synergies that could be realised.

For the FCC, the demand for locally supplied electricity will vary according to the progress of the works. The tunnel boring machines (TBM) require a stable, reinforced electricity network. Different location scenarios are envisaged for the TBM. The following scenario is the most appropriate from a technical standpoint:

- Site PA: 2 TBM: 16 MW
- Site PB: 0 TBM: 3 MW
- Site PD: 2 TBM: 16 MW
- Site PF: 0 TBM: 3 MW
- Site PG: 2 TBM: 16 MW
- Site PH: 0 TBM: 3 MW
- Site PJ: 2 TBM: 16 MW

¹⁹ <https://www.cc-genevois.fr/fr/la-collectivite-et-son-territoire/decouvrir-les-grands-projets/le-forage-de-matailly-moissey>

²⁰ <https://www.tpf-i.fr/portfolio/construction-dune-station-de-traitement-deau-potable-2/>, <https://www.tpf-i.fr/portfolio/station-de-production-deau-potable-28-000-m%C2%B3-j/>

- Site PL: 0 TBM: 3 MW

The existing networks will need to be reinforced as they are unable to meet the demand. The reinforcements carried out for the construction phase of the FCC, to which CERN will have contributed financially, will only be used for this phase and will therefore be available for the local area afterwards. For example, such network reinforcements could help to support the use of electric vehicles (EVs). They could enable electric charging points to be deployed in areas where the network is not adapted to such vehicles (see annex 8.4 for details of the EV charging network and the existing charging points put in place by Syane in Haute-Savoie). Motorway service stations that could become access points for the construction of the FCC are also possible locations for these charging points. The study will identify the network reinforcements required, the sites that can be considered and the synergies for reuse in accordance with local needs.

4.4. POTENTIAL REUSE OF THE LHC TUNNEL

The HL-LHC research programme will come to an end around 2040. The LHC tunnel has a circumference of 27 km and a diameter of 3.8 metres. The structure also includes four large caverns, which house the experiment detectors. **If the LHC is not used during the operation phase of the FCC-hh**, these caverns may offer numerous possibilities for reuse after the HL-LHC programme has been concluded. They are located at a depth of between 80 and 150 metres. The temperature of the tunnel is between 22 and 26 degrees at steady state. The caverns are presented in Table 13:

Table 13: Size of LHC detectors and experiment caverns.

Experiment	ATLAS – P1	CMS – P5	LHCb – P8	ALICE – P2
Location	Meyrin	Cessy	Ferney-Voltaire	Saint-Genis-Pouilly
Experiment cavern size (L x W x H)	53 m x 30 m x 35 m	53 m x 24 m x 24 m	70 m x 16 m x 19 m	53 m x 15 m x 23 m
Experiment cavern volume	47 000 m ³	32 000 m ³	23 000 m ³	22 000 m ³
Shaft size (diameter)	2 shafts of 18 m and 12.9 m	20.5 m	10 m	23 m
Detector size (L x W x H)	46 m x 26 m x 26 m	21 m x 15 m x 15 m	21 m x 10 m x 13 m	26 m x 16 m x 16 m
Detector weight	7000 tonnes	15 500 tonnes	5600 tonnes	10 000 tonnes

Service caverns are also located near the experiment caverns and at other points of the LHC, notably Point 4 and Point 6. They measure between 16 and 84 m in length, between 14 and 20 m in width and 13 m in height, and each is equipped with one or two shafts of between 5 and 12 m in diameter. These service caverns house the technical installations for the LHC machine. The tunnel has all the facilities needed to provide the machine with electricity, water, telecommunications and ventilation, as well as safety and access equipment. The caverns that house the experiments could be used in several ways, as could the service caverns and the collider tunnel, depending on the aims and the technical resources required. Before any potential project can be implemented, the LHC will have to have ceased operation and have been dismantled.

The following list sets out some initial ideas for developing these underground spaces:

- Installation of water reservoirs for the recovery of additional water (from the Jura, for example) during wet periods and for the supply of water in times of shortage.
- Storage of recovered heat.
- Plant for washing reusable packaging using heat available from the FCC (see annex 8.5).
- Archive storage.
- Conversion to cellars for storing wine and/or cheese or other foodstuffs.
- Installation of greenhouses to reuse the heat available from the FCC, possibly with the installation of vertical trusses in the shafts (see annex 8.6).
- Aquaponics, hydroponics or a park that reuses the heat available from the FCC (see, for example, the Lowline Lab project described in annex 8.7).
- Tests and prototypes requiring unlit areas.
- Creation of FabLabs (surface sites).
- Creation of educational spaces (surface sites).

This list is not exhaustive and many possibilities exist.

5. POTENTIAL OPPORTUNITIES AND SYNERGIES LINKED TO THE PRESENCE OF THE FCC INFRASTRUCTURE

5.1. CREATION OF SUSTAINABLE SCIENTIFIC TOURISM

5.1.1. Tourism at CERN

CERN attracts many visitors because of its leading role in particle physics research. CERN currently welcomes around 150 000 visitors a year and expects to welcome more than 300 000 in the future, following the opening of the Science Gateway in October 2023²¹. Thanks to this new centre, the city of Geneva is included in the New York Times list of cities to visit in 2024²². Just three months after its opening, the Science Gateway has already welcomed 88 000 visitors. Groups (organised tours) account for 55% of the total number of visitors and individuals the remaining 45%. According to a study on CERN's cultural impact²³, the average length of stay in the area is four days and the average local²⁴ spend during that time is €528²⁵ in the case of group visitors and €628 in the case of individual visitors. From the beginning of the construction of the FCC-ee, it is expected that 52 000 people per year will visit the infrastructure and experiments, at least 130 000 will visit CERN exhibitions (Science Gateway) and 67 000 will visit the HL-LHC. During the operation phase, 56 000 people are expected to visit the infrastructure and experiments, 205 000 the exhibits and 38 000 the HL-LHC. Tour groups come mainly to visit CERN; however, they also visit other cultural sites in the region. Annex 8.8 shows a sample school group itinerary.

5.1.2. Development of visitor centres and visit tours

Visitor centres could be created on the FCC scientific sites in order to present research related to the experiments, show the control room and allow access to the detectors where possible. One or more visit points would thus be established in Haute-Savoie. As a reminder, points on opposite sides of the ring, i.e. sites PA and PG, and sites PD and PJ, are separated by a distance of 40 km.

A visitor centre generally comprises the following elements:

- An information room
- Access to the control room
- Access to view the bottom of the shaft
- Access to the service cavern during operation
- Access to the detector when the collider is not in operation
- An exhibit, ideally an interactive one
- Catering facilities, a shop selling souvenirs and other products.

The presence of local services, such as catering, accommodation and transport, is an incentive for visitors.

The tourist attractions in the vicinity of each of the four scientific sites envisaged for the FCC will need to be studied. Visits will be possible from the start of construction. In fact, the construction site will be a tourist attraction in its own right. Structures of this kind are unusual, which makes them interesting in terms of the challenges and problems associated with underground work. The worksites can become spaces for information, discussion and immersion in the project. The TELT (Lyon–Turin) project, for example, has a permanent

²¹ <https://visit.cern/fr/science-gateway>

²² <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2024/travel/places-to-travel-destinations-2024.html>

²³ I. Crespo Garrido (2018), *Cultural effects at CERN*, <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2649022/files/CERN-ACC-2018-0048.pdf>

²⁴ Accommodation, food and drink, souvenirs, cultural visits (excluding CERN), transport in the region

²⁵ CHF/EUR exchange rate in 2021: 1 CHF = 0.964 EUR

exhibition for the general public, featuring immersive displays providing information about the project and the valley's main tourist and cultural attractions.

In 2022²⁶, there were 207.3 million overnight stays in hotels in mainland France, with Haute-Savoie ranked as the 13th most popular French department for such stays (including hotels and campsites), at around 6.9 million. The Department of Ain was in 58th place, with around 1.6 million overnight stays. Haute-Savoie accounts for 21% of overnight stays in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region, just after the Rhône department (24%), with Ain accounting for 4%. Table 14 shows the most popular tourist attractions in the two departments, each attracting more than 100 000 visitors per year²⁷:

Table 14: Most popular tourist attractions in Haute-Savoie and Ain.

Haute-Savoie	Ain
Chamonix-Mont-Blanc cable cars (Mer de Glace, Aiguille du Midi, Brévent); Father Christmas's village at Saint-Blaise; Musée-Château d'Annecy; Grand Parc d'Andilly (theme park); Gorges du Fier at Lovagny.	Medieval town of Pérouges; Bird park; CERN.

The region is renowned for its cheese-making. In order to showcase the richness of the region, an itinerary comprising 72 sites in Savoie and Haute-Savoie has been created, known as *La Route des Fromages de Savoie*²⁸ (The Savoie Cheese Route) (Figure 9). With a view to promoting sustainable tourism and the discovery of local products, "cycling and cheese" tours are increasingly being developed in this area and even further afield (see annex 8.9). It could be interesting to combine this regional tourism with scientific tourism.

As an example, in order to promote the sciences, *Science & Vie* magazine, the NGO *Objectif Sciences International* and the French *Conservatoire national des arts et métiers* (National Conservatory of Arts and Crafts, CNAM) organise *Les Rencontres Terra Scientifica*²⁹ in Paris – an international week of participatory science and scientific discovery. During this week, numerous exhibitors, including research centres, associations, travel agencies, the tourism industry and nature parks, offer activities and trips linked to their scientific activities. Participatory scientific tourism is therefore already a well-established and attractive concept.

²⁶ INSEE (2023), *Fréquentation des hébergements collectifs touristiques en 2022*, <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/2012672>

²⁷ *Observatoire Savoie Mont-Blanc*, 2023 edition, <https://www.pro.savoie-mont-blanc.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/chiffres-cles-savoie-mont-blanc-2023-savoie-haute-savoie.pdf>

²⁸ <https://www.fromagesdesavoie.fr/content/uploads/2023/05/LESSENTIEL-2023-web.pdf>

²⁹ <https://www.terra-scientifica.com/Terra-Scientifica-le-Rendez-Vous-des-Voyages-qui-ont-du-Sens.html>

Figure 9: La Route des Fromages de Savoie. Source: La Route des Fromages de Savoie.

The following paragraphs describe a selection of local tourist attractions other than the most well-known ones (such as Chamonix-Mont-Blanc). The main sites in the list, which is not exhaustive, are in Haute-Savoie since the scientific sites are located in this department.

5.1.2.1. Scientific site PA – Ferney-Voltaire

The ATLAS experiment at the LHC in Meyrin will remain primarily a visitor centre. It will be accessible all year round because the LHC will no longer be in operation.

However, site PA could be configured in the same way as Point 8 (LHCb), which features an information room, access to the control room and access to the underground detector. The surrounding infrastructure, the local services in Ferney-Voltaire and the availability of public transport make site PA an attraction that is accessible to all.

5.1.2.2. Scientific site PD – Nangy

There are no tourist attractions directly in this area. Table 15 shows some examples of tourist activities in the area around site PD³⁰ (up to a distance of 50 km).

³⁰ Especially those to the north of site PD, since those located further south and in the centre will be presented in connection with sites PG and PJ.

Table 15: Tourist attractions in the area around site PD.

Tourist attraction	Explanation	Commune
Hiking in the Salève		Collonges-sur-Salève
Hiking in the Voirons mountain range		Machilly
Walking along the banks of the Arve		Contamine-sur-Arve to Bonneville
Medieval village of Yvoire		Yvoire
Castle of Ripaille (castle, cellar, vineyards), Pôle culturel de la Visitation (cultural centre) and Valvital thermal baths		Thonon-les-Bains
Grange au Lac concert hall	Famous for the <i>Rencontres Musicales d'Évian</i> music festival.	Évian-les-Bains
<i>Centre Alpin de Recherche sur les Réseaux Trophiques et les Écosystèmes Limniques</i> (Alpine Centre for Research on Trophic Networks and Limnic Ecosystems) (CARTEL),	Public lectures. Joint research unit of INRAE ³¹ and <i>Université Savoie Mont Blanc</i> (USMB).	Évian-les-Bains
GAEC Savoie-Gascogne dairy farm	<i>Route des Fromages de Savoie</i> . Guided tour of the farm and educational workshops on animal husbandry and production: cow milking, cheese-making demonstrations, flour-making, calf-feeding, tasting sessions.	Marin
<i>Le Tour de la Vallée Verte</i> cycling and cheese route	Visits to farms and cheesemakers along the cycling route.	Annemasse
Arve Valley industries	The Arve Valley is renowned for micromechanics, and some businesses offer tours of their facilities.	Arve Valley

The analysis of local services (see section Synergies with local services^{5.2}) shows that the range of amenities (restaurants, hotels, public transport) is generally adequate.

³¹ *Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement* (French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food, & Environment (INRAE))

Box 6: Discussions with the Haute-Savoie Departmental Council

The Departmental Council would like this site to be an educational centre that promotes the Arve Valley, as well as a tourist site with a visitor centre. This could be done on the basis of the training opportunities set out in the training and education section of this report. In addition, the report on the analysis of the needs and options for an additional FCC hub (Alix, 2024) shows that, based on the multicriteria analysis, site PD could be the best option for an activity hub³².

5.1.2.3. Scientific site PD – Charvonnex/Groisy

These two communes are not, strictly speaking, tourist destinations. They are, however, close to many of the points of interest shown in Table 16:

Table 16: Tourist attractions in the area around site PG.

Tourist attraction	Explanation	Commune
Glères Plateau	A key site for the French Resistance. Hiking trails in summer and winter (ski touring). Educational visits to farms and manufacturers of dairy products (<i>Route des fromages de Savoie</i>). "Tour des Glères" cycling and cheese route ("difficult" category).	Fillière
Lake Annecy, Musée-Château		Annecy
LAPP (<i>Laboratoire d'Annecy de Physique des Particules</i> – Annecy Particle Physics Laboratory) and EUTOPIA; <i>La Turbine</i> (scientific and cultural centre in Annecy)	Numerous conferences, debates and meetings on different scientific subjects.	Annecy
Gorges du Fier		Lovagny
Menthon-Saint-Bernard Castle		Menthon-Saint-Bernard
Semnoz mountain	Hiking and ski resort	Near to Annecy
Educational farm in Thônes	<i>Route des Fromages de Savoie</i> .	Thônes

³² Activity hub = a place where researchers and scientists from the FCC research programme can meet. The hub would complement the two main existing sites (Meyrin and Prévessin).

Box 7: Discussions with the representatives of the communes of Groisy and Charvonnex.

During meetings with the representatives of the communes of Groisy and Charvonnex, the idea of creating a visitor centre linked to the scientific site was discussed. In Groisy, the possibility of turning the train station into a strategic multimodal hub is currently under study. The recycling company Excoffier is vacating its 2.5-hectare site and new activities for the site are being considered; another company is also vacating a one-hectare premises. The creation of a scientific site would be an opportunity to develop this area. This project would complement the construction of a new secondary school opposite the existing Parmelan secondary school. The two schools will eventually cater for more than 1400 pupils, mainly from the Pays de Fillière. In addition, the Campus de Groisy³³, which has 1000 pupils, is also expanding. The region is therefore ideally suited to hosting this kind of service. The discussions also covered the land adjacent to site PG; however, it would be difficult to build on it as it is very steep.

Other development opportunities mentioned include:

- The creation of a cultural and scientific centre linked to site PG: tours of the site, presentations, workshops, exhibitions, educational programmes for secondary schools.
- The creation of a high-quality restaurant, a relaxation area with a heated swimming pool (it would be useful to look into the new swimming pool project at Epagny-Metz-Tessy) taking advantage of the exceptional view of the surrounding landscape and mountains (the Aravis mountain range, for example) and the natural environment. Access for pedestrians and cyclists from the motorway service station would make this an even more attractive option.
- The development of science-based local tourism.
- The creation of buildings and offices for scientists and service providers.
- Market gardening or another agricultural activity³⁴ (such as an aquaponics farm, to take advantage of the heat available at site PG).
- The development of a range of accommodation and catering services linked to the site.

Local services are currently limited. The creation of a restaurant and possibly accommodation could therefore be an attractive option. It will also be necessary to ensure good accessibility between site PG, Groisy station and the motorway service station 800 m away.

5.1.2.4. Scientific site PJ – Vulbens/Charvonnex

These two communes are not tourist destinations. They are, however, close to many of the points of interest shown in Table 17:

³³ Training centre for apprentices in the food, catering, pharmacy and floristry industries.

³⁴ Greater Annecy aims to improve its food self-sufficiency.

Table 17: Tourist attractions in the area around site PJ.

Tourist attraction	Explanation	Commune
Stopover village on the ViaRhôna cycle route (see annex 8.10)	An 815-km cycle route linking Lake Geneva in Switzerland to the Mediterranean. Between 20 000 and 50 000 cyclists used the section between Geneva and Seyssel in 2022, 50% of them for leisure purposes, spending an average of €65 per day ³⁵ . According to the same study, every 1 km of the ViaRhôna that is developed generates €53 000 in spending in the region each year. If it hosts a visitor centre, the PJ scientific site could enhance the tourist appeal of the stopover village of Vulbens and thus increase spending in the area.	Vulbens
Vuache Mountain	Hiking	Close to Dingy-en-Vuache
Fort l'Ecluse	Fortified military structure offering tours, a theatre and concerts.	Léaz (Ain)
Génissiat Dam	CNR ³⁶ organises tours of the dam site.	Génissiat (Ain)
<i>Centre d'Immersion Éducatif et Ludique</i> (immersive educational centre)	SIVALOR ³⁷ offers an educational tour on the subject of waste recovery.	Valserhône (Ain)
Vitam sports centre	Water park, wellness and spa, fitness, climbing, squash and badminton.	Neydens
Grand Parc d'Andilly (Christmas Park, Father Christmas's Village, Medieval Park)	The park hosts different activities, depending on the season.	Andilly/Saint Blaise
GAEC <i>Au Coucher du Soleil</i> educational farm	<i>Route des Fromages de Savoie</i> .	Jonzier-Epagny

³⁵ *Étude sur la fréquentation et les retombées économiques de ViaRhôna, 2022, Auvergne Rhône-Alpes, <https://www.viarhona.com/espace-pro/actualites/etude-sur-la-frequentation-et-les-retombees-economiques-de-la-viarhona>*

³⁶ *Compagnie Nationale du Rhône* (electricity company)

³⁷ *Syndicat Intercommunal de VALORisation* (Intercommunal Association for Waste Recovery)

Box 8: Discussions with the representatives of the communes of Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens.

During meetings with the representatives of the communes Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulbens, the idea of creating a visitor centre linked to the scientific site was discussed. Such a centre would be realised in conjunction with the development of the Grands Chavannoux area, in particular the construction of a new secondary school with capacity for 750 pupils, the expansion of the Intermarché supermarket and the construction of a new police station.

Other development opportunities mentioned include:

- The creation of a cultural and scientific centre linked to site PG: tours of the site, presentations, workshops, exhibitions, educational programmes for the secondary school in Vuache.
- The development of science-based tourism.
- The further development of the Grands Chavannoux area, in the land available opposite it (close to the new police station).
- The development of a local restaurant, or accommodation, linked to the site.
- A swimming pool using heat from site PJ.
- The creation of a secondary school.

Local services are currently limited; the creation of a restaurant and possibly accommodation could therefore be an attractive option. It will also be necessary to ensure that site PJ is easily accessible by public transport.

In conclusion, it is appropriate to envisage the creation of tourist attractions that combine science, mountains and local produce. A study is under way to develop a tourism concept that takes all these aspects into account.

5.2. DEVELOPMENT OF LOCAL SERVICES

5.2.1. Services on the CERN campus

Local services can vary. In the broadest sense, they can be defined as the local services available to a given community or area. Catering and accommodation options are of particular interest because they are an everyday essential for those coming to work on each site.

Up to 12 000 people are present on the CERN site on a given day. The Laboratory has three restaurants³⁸ and several cafeterias, three hostels/hotels and a partnership with a low-cost housing complex (Foyer Residence Schuman)³⁹. It is essential to have catering facilities on site or within a 10-minute drive. Other services are also available on the CERN campus.

5.2.2. Synergies with local services

Annex 8.11 shows a map of the restaurants (all types) and accommodation (more than five rooms) available within a 10-minute drive of each site. Generally speaking, each site is served by several restaurants within the defined perimeter. Accommodation, however, is very limited; there is no accommodation within the perimeter of site PJ, and only low-capacity holiday cottages are available in the case of site PH. Partnerships could be established to create synergies with local services (existing or new). The opportunities at each site are as follows (Table 18):

Table 18: Local services within a 10-minute radius of each site.

Site	Restaurants	Accommodation	Potential synergies
PA	> 40 restaurants	> 30 hotels	CERN sites close by
PB	> 40 restaurants	13 hotels	Centre du Lullier restaurant (HEPIA/CFPNE) (1.5 km)
PD	28 restaurants	8 hotels/holiday cottages	Findrol business park: "Open Pole 74" with Campanile Hotel (70 rooms, 3*), a co-working and meeting space, a restaurant and a micro-crèche (1 km). Hôtel Ibis Budget, 76 rooms, 2* (500 m). CHAL hospital restaurant (safety permitting).
PF	19 restaurants	2 hotels	
PG	12 restaurants	4 hotels/holiday cottages	Development of Groisy station (see Box 7: Discussions with the representatives of the communes of Groisy and Charvonnex.).
PH	10 restaurants	2 holiday cottages	Chosal educational farm: caters only for visiting groups, training and seminars (5 km).
PJ	15 restaurants	0 accommodation	Development of the Grands Chavannoux area (see Box 8: Discussions with the representatives of the communes of Dingy-en-Vuache and Vulpens.).
PL	17 restaurants	6 hotels	CERN sites close by.

Only restaurants and accommodation are taken into consideration. However, synergies may be possible with other local services, such as transport services (see section 5.3), childcare services (crèches for the children of

³⁸ With an average of 1000 meals served daily and an average spend of 14 CHF per meal.

³⁹ 151 of the 260 rooms available are allocated to CERN.

local people, CERN personnel and visitors), schools (for children of the personnel, international schools), sports clubs, healthcare services (see section 5.5), etc. Synergies linked to local services will emerge as the project progresses.

5.3. IMPROVEMENT OF MOBILITY OPTIONS

5.3.1. Mobility at CERN

CERN offers a wide range of mobility options for journeys between its sites, as well as in the region. These include cars, push bicycles, electric bicycles, electric scooters, e-scooters and shuttles serving the various CERN sites. These means of transport are mainly used for professional purposes.

As for commuting (journeys between home and work), a 2018 study on mobility at CERN⁴⁰ found that 10% of respondents (387 people) used public transport to travel to CERN and 13% (480 people) came by bicycle. Improving public transport services and safety for soft modes of transport would help to boost soft mobility.

CERN is served by a stop for buses and trams (terminus). It is generally quick and easy to travel within Geneva by tram. However, transport in France and the surrounding towns is less well developed; services are sometimes less frequent, which results in longer journey times. According to the study, 26% of respondents living in Switzerland used public transport, compared to just 3% of respondents living in France.

Synergies with local public transport services must therefore be created. This can only be achieved in cooperation with the Host States.

5.3.2. Roads

Studies are under way to analyse the access roads of all of the FCC surface sites. The establishment of an infrastructure like the FCC could help to improve certain roads. New roads may also be needed to ensure better access. These new roads could be used later on by the local community. They could also be designed to incorporate cycle routes, thus facilitating soft modes of transport and journeys between neighbouring communes. The studies under way will provide a more precise assessment of the potential benefits associated with these improvements. The report summarising the constraints and opportunities associated with the site of the Future Circular Collider (FCC) presents the preliminary work carried out with regard to the various access options⁴¹. Annex 8.12 shows the distances in kilometres and minutes between each site.

5.3.3. Railway

The region is served by the Léman Express (see map in annex 8.13); however, the journey between Annecy and Geneva can be long. In addition to road links, rail access is also examined in the report on the constraints and opportunities associated with the FCC site. Subsequent studies will enable synergies to be identified more clearly. One possible synergy could be reopening the partially disused Pied du Jura line (see annex 8.14). This line connects Valserhône (formerly Bellegarde-sur-Valserine) and Gex, passing through Péron and St-Jean-de-Gonville, which are located 5 km from Challex (site PL). Nonetheless, a more realistic option would be to reopen the old station in Collonges in order to use it for the transport of materials for the FCC and for the removal of excavated material during the construction phase of the project. Once restored, this station would be of great value to the region. This scenario, which would require the engagement of the State, the region, the department and the SNCF (French national rail company), has garnered strong interest.

Another important consideration would be to increase the frequency of Léman Express trains stopping at Groisy from once an hour to once every 30 minutes. This would make site PG more attractive for both employees and visitors. Nevertheless, since this line only has a single track, this improvement is not yet feasible. The arrival of

⁴⁰ <https://home.cern/sites/default/files/file/cern-community/Enque%CC%82te-Mobilite%CC%81.pdf>

⁴¹ J. Gutleber et al. (2024), *Synthèse des contraintes et opportunités d'implantation du Futur Collisionneur Circulaire (FCC)*, <https://zenodo.org/records/10369593>

the FCC would provide an opportunity to create a route with two tracks where trains could pass each other, thereby allowing the frequency of the service to be increased. Such a project would take at least 10 years to complete; it would need to be undertaken as part of a collaboration between the region, the department and the State, and an agreement would need to be signed with the SNCF. Groisy and Charvonnex have shown strong interest in this development, which would add value to the two communes and reduce road traffic in the directions of Annecy and Geneva.

5.3.4. Public transport and soft mobility

Some of the communes in the vicinity of the planned location of the FCC are more developed than others, so public transport options vary between them. A large part of this area (in Switzerland and France) is served by Transports Publics Genevois (TPG), namely sites PA, PB, PD, PJ and PL (see annex 8.15); sites PD and PF are served by the Proxim'iti network (see annex 8.16), and site PG is served by the Sibra network (see annex 8.17). Annex 8.18 shows the minimum transport times between one site and another. It would be very complicated and time consuming to use the public transport network in its current state to travel between the sites.

The work undertaken to improve the network will depend on the number of people at each site, where they live and, for the scientific sites, the additional attractions developed there (visitor centre, restaurant, etc.).

The provision of a CERN shuttle bus between CERN and the FCC sites and/or between the different FCC sites and/or from the various train stations would generally serve to facilitate more synergies and would also be available to people outside CERN. In order to take advantage of the increased capacity of the electricity network, which would be reinforced ahead of the construction of the FCC, electric shuttle buses could be used and charging stations could be installed on the surface sites. Another potential synergy would be to develop an e-bike sharing scheme for use for journeys between CERN and the region. There are currently no bicycle-sharing systems in operation near the surface sites. This would be particularly useful for scientific sites offering tourist activities.

5.3.4.1. Site PA – Ferney-Voltaire, France

This site, which is located near CERN (Meyrin and Prévessin sites), suffers from traffic congestion. Improving public transport services, ideally by opening a tram line between the two CERN sites and Ferney-Voltaire, would be useful.

5.3.4.2. Site PB – Presinge/Choulex

This site has poor public transport links and is located far from the other sites. Several facilities near the site, such as HEPIA (Geneva School of Landscape, Engineering and Architecture) in Lully, would benefit from improved public transport.

5.3.4.3. Site PD – Nangy

This site is under pressure from road traffic (especially in the direction of Switzerland and La Roche-sur-Foron). There are some bus routes to and from the CHAL hospital as well as a park and ride scheme. However, the other sites are a long way away. It would be beneficial to improve public transport links.

5.3.4.4. Site PF – Eteaux/La Roche-sur-Foron

Site PF is not directly served by public transport; the nearest stops are Eteaux chef-lieu and La Roche-sur-Foron station. The station has fairly good connections (especially to sites PD and PG) via the Léman Express. A shuttle bus linking the station to site PF (6 minutes by car) would be useful, and possibly a cycle path.

5.3.4.5. Site PG – Charvonnex/Groisy

At present, site PG is not very well served by public transport. The Léman Express does, however, stop at Groisy station. Moreover, as per the 2030 mobility plan for Greater Annecy⁴², it is planned to transform this station into a multimodal hub, with improved train and bus services and the establishment of cycle links. The creation of road access to the north of site PG would provide a quicker and easier link to Groisy (schools and station) and would be in synergy with the development of the bus station. A shuttle bus and a cycle route linking the station to site PG would be needed to provide better access to the scientific site for members of the personnel, as well as tourists and school groups.

5.3.4.6. Site PH – Cercier/Marlioz

There are no public transport services to this site, and the rural setting does not necessarily justify the opening of a new line (to be studied). A CERN shuttle bus seems to be the best solution. This shuttle bus could be linked to the experiment sites PJ, PG or PD or to the potential additional hub⁴³. It would also be worth exploring the possibility of a shuttle service from Meyrin, passing through sites PL, PJ and PH. This solution would improve transport options for the people of Challex.

5.3.4.7. Site PJ – Dingy-en-Vuache/Vulbens

This site has few public transport options and is far from the other sites. Public transport links to Geneva and/or Annecy should be improved in a way that is consistent with the level of development of this scientific site (cultural centre and urban development). One potential synergy is the establishment of a shuttle service between CERN and site PH, passing through sites PL and PJ. For greater synergy, the site should also be linked to nearby cycle routes, in particular the one that connects up with the ViaRhôna.

5.3.4.8. Site PL – Challex

The commune of Challex is isolated. It is not served by French public transport networks and is served by only one Swiss TPG bus route, which operates infrequently. Although it would be useful to have a more direct bus service, this would be difficult to justify given the size of the commune and the fact that site PL will only be a technical site. One possible synergy would be for CERN to provide a shuttle bus that would transport CERN users from Meyrin to Challex, and even to other sites, and that would also be accessible to people outside CERN. A study will need to be carried out to determine the feasibility of this solution. If the Jura line were to be reopened with stations at Péron and St-Jean-de-Gonville, a bus route linking Challex with one of these stations might be useful, thus improving services between this commune and the other French communes.

⁴² <https://www.calameo.com/read/0043200638e24ca0fc535>

⁴³ L. Alix (2024), *Étude des besoins et des options pour un pôle supplémentaire FCC, CNRS et CERN*

5.4. PROMOTION OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING

5.4.1. Collaboration with universities

The project is to be built in an area with several universities and higher education institutions. The Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region is home to many universities and research centres, such as the CEA (Alternative and Atomic Energies Agency), CNRS (National Centre for Scientific Research) and INRAE (National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment). The map in Figure 10 shows the location of the institutions for higher education, research and innovation. Close to the FCC site is the Annecy campus and a satellite site of the Université Savoie-Mont-Blanc (USMB), which comprises a University Institute of Technology (IUT), an engineering school, an Institute of Business Administration (IAE), the USMB research centres (SYMME – Laboratory System and Materials for Mechatronics and IREGE – Institute for Research in Management and Economics) and the CNRS with the LAPP (Annecy Particle Physics Laboratory) and LAPTh (Annecy Theoretical Physics Laboratory). The LAPP already works closely with CERN. The arrival of the FCC could strengthen collaboration with universities and research centres in the Haute-Savoie region, in particular the USMB and the LAPP/CNRS, by increasing their participation and involvement in CERN's programmes.

Figure 10: Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes: locations of the main institutions for higher education, research and innovation. Source: French Ministry of Higher Education and Research.

Neighbouring parts of Switzerland, such as the Canton of Geneva and the Canton of Vaud, are also home to many universities, higher education institutions and universities of applied sciences. In the Canton of Geneva, these include the University of Geneva (UNIGE), the Graduate Institute of International and Development Studies (IHEID) and the University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland (HES-SO), which includes the Geneva School of Landscape, Engineering and Architecture (HEPIA) (see the map of universities in Figure 11). In the Canton of Vaud, these include the University of Lausanne (UNIL), the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Lausanne (EPFL), HES-SO and the Vaud University of Education (HEP). The maps in annex 8.19 show the location and size of universities of applied sciences and teacher training colleges in Switzerland.

Situation et taille des hautes écoles universitaires en Suisse, en 2022/23

Figure 11: Universities in Switzerland. Source: Swiss Federal Statistical Office.

5.4.2. Collaboration in vocational training

Both for the construction phase and the operation phase, the FCC project will require technical expertise in a number of areas. During the civil engineering phase, training opportunities could be created through regional contracts and support programmes aimed at local and regional businesses (see the approach adopted for the Grand Chantier Lyon-Turin (TELT) in annex 8.20, which is an example of local opportunities linked to the construction of a large infrastructure project in a region).

For the equipment installation phase, and throughout the operating phase, CERN will be able to offer training opportunities in sectors such as industry and construction, in areas including machining, polishing, electrical installations, air conditioning and welding. It would be appropriate to develop high-quality apprenticeships with French schools. Apprenticeships already exist at CERN but are only available in conjunction with Swiss programmes. This could be an opportunity to develop such training in Haute-Savoie. Apprenticeships involving

Swiss schools⁴⁴ are currently available in the following areas: electronics, mechanics, documentary information, physics laboratory technician.

Moreover, CERN could work together with local businesses (particularly those in the Arve Valley specialising in mechatronics) and students to develop educational programmes for students with the aim of improving the technical skills of young people and benefiting CERN and companies. This collaboration would capitalise on CERN's solid expertise in the development of cutting-edge technologies and that of local companies in fields such as precision mechanics. Involving students in this way would facilitate technology transfer. This approach could also be expanded to areas other than those mentioned above.

The following training centres are located in the vicinity of the proposed FCC site: MFR⁴⁵ Champ Molliaz in Cranves-Sales, CFAI⁴⁶ in Thyez and Annecy, and AFPI⁴⁷ and Tetras⁴⁸ in Annecy. These centres all offer technological and industrial training in the form of sandwich courses, from the vocational baccalaureate to the engineering diploma. The CFAI, AFPI and Tetras belong to the Pôle Formation Haute-Savoie (Haute-Savoie training centre), under the aegis of the CSM⁴⁹ and of the UIMM⁵⁰, which supports both companies and students to ensure quality training through apprenticeships. This network could therefore represent a strong synergy for high-quality training linked to the local economy. *Pôle Formation* is a national network of training centres and is therefore present in other regions of France. Figure 12 shows the *Pôle Formation* network in Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes and the Swiss vocational schools that have a partnership with CERN.

⁴⁴ Vocational schools in Lausanne (EPCL and EPSIC), CFPT (School of Electronics and Mechatronics)

⁴⁵ Apprentice training centre (CFA) for HVAC and sanitation engineering, refrigeration, renewable energies and welding, <https://mfr-cranves-sales.fr/>

⁴⁶ Training centre for industrial apprentices, <https://www.cfai74.com/>

⁴⁷ Continuing education centre for industrial trades, <https://www.afpi-etudoc.com/>

⁴⁸ Created by the Université Savoie Mont Blanc (USMB) and CSM Haute-Savoie, <https://www.tetras.univ-smb.fr/>

⁴⁹ Haute-Savoie Metallurgy Trade Association, <https://www.csm-haute-savoie.com/blog/>

⁵⁰ French Union of Metallurgy Industries and Trades, <https://uimm.lafabriquedelavenir.fr/industrie/>

Figure 12: Pôle Formation network in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region, with centres in Haute-Savoie, and the vocational schools offering apprenticeships with CERN. Source: Pole Formation Haute-Savoie.

5.4.3. Collaborations with schools and colleges

CERN currently has links with several schools through various programmes, such as Women and Girls in Science and Technology⁵¹, as well as through lab workshops⁵² at Science Gateway⁵³, science shows⁵⁴ and guided tours⁵⁵. However, to fully take advantage of this opportunity, a methodical and systematic approach still needs to be implemented, under the direction of the Host States.

The FCC's arrival in an area with no existing CERN connections could boost the public's understanding of and familiarity with the Organization and its research programme, thereby encouraging local schools and colleges to visit (see annex 8.21). The development of each of the scientific sites and the cultural and tourist attractions within them will be an important factor in establishing partnerships and attracting visitors.

Relationships between local schools and colleges and the scientific sites can be cultivated in several ways:

- Educational visits: guided tours of the facilities, presentations on the research being carried out.
- Educational programmes: workshops on science, technology and engineering.
- Conferences and presentations on different subjects, in schools or at the visitor centres, enabling links to be forged with researchers and professionals. Larger conferences could also be organised in the area where the FCC is based.

⁵¹ <https://voisins.web.cern.ch/fr/women-and-girls-science-and-technology>

⁵² <https://sciencegateway.cern/fr/lab>

⁵³ <https://visit.cern/fr>

⁵⁴ <https://sciencegateway.cern/fr/shows>

⁵⁵ <https://sciencegateway.cern/fr/guided-tours>

- Teaching resources: provision of teaching resources developed by CERN that can be used by teachers to enrich classroom lessons and activities.
- Collaborative projects: schools could carry out simple scientific experiments in class and discuss them with CERN researchers during their visits to the site.

The possibilities are numerous, and most of these proposals would also be open to the general public, in line with the principle of open science. These opportunities would be offered on a smaller scale, with Science Gateway in Meyrin remaining the main venue for open science.

The presence of CERN and its staff in the local area led to the creation of the international secondary school based in Ferney-Voltaire and Saint-Genis-Pouilly. This school could serve as a model for the development of an international secondary school in Haute-Savoie.

Box 9: Discussions with the communes of Vulbens and Groisy.

Meetings with local authorities have confirmed their interest in establishing partnerships between their schools, in particular secondary schools, and the scientific sites located nearby. This is the case in Vulbens, which has a new secondary school for over 700 pupils, located in the Grands Chavannoux area, just over a kilometre from the PJ scientific site. The same applies to the Le Parmelan secondary school in Groisy and the future secondary school just opposite it, which is due to open by 2026. These two establishments are located just over 2 km from the PG scientific site and will welcome a total of over 1400 pupils. Strong synergies can therefore be created with these two communes; they should be developed together with the competent authorities of the Department of Haute-Savoie.

The proximity of site PB to the Champ-Dollon prison could represent an interesting opportunity. The REPR⁵⁶ foundation supports the friends and families of prisoners. In particular, it organises play/activity workshops for prisoners and their children. Skills workshops are also offered within the prison. It is becoming increasingly common for prisons to offer educational programmes, personal development activities or cultural workshops to facilitate prisoners' social and professional reintegration. Given the proximity of the FCC, science-related workshops or teaching tools could be provided.

The Host States' commitment to developing opportunities in this area will bring significant benefits. According to the OECD⁵⁷, every euro or Swiss franc invested in improving education for young people generates a return of around 10 cents per year.

⁵⁶ Relais Enfants Parents Romands, <https://www.repr.ch/Presentation-228>

⁵⁷ <https://www.oecd.org/education/school/50293148.pdf>

5.5. COLLABORATION WITH THE EMERGENCY SERVICES

5.5.1. CERN and its agreements with Host States regarding emergencies

CERN's facilities and particle colliders are complex environments that present a unique set of risks; this calls for careful preparation and a rapid response in the event of an emergency. In emergency situations, the responsiveness of the fire brigade is crucial to prevent major damage, ensure the safety of personnel and avoid any major disruption to research activities. It is therefore essential that fire stations be located close to each surface site. In addition to the emergency response aspect, there are other benefits for the region.

A tripartite agreement⁵⁸ was signed by CERN and its two Host States in 2016. It covers mutual assistance between the emergency services of CERN, Switzerland and France in the event of emergencies on the CERN sites and in the surrounding area. The benefits of this collaboration can be divided into three categories:

- **Intervention:** when an intervention is under way on the territory and local reinforcement is required, the agreement gives each party the possibility to request assistance from the other parties. This is all the more beneficial given that CERN has equipment and expertise in certain fields (notably radiation protection) that the Host States do not have, and vice versa. Thus, all parties can benefit from mutual exchanges. On several occasions, the CERN Fire and Rescue service has provided assistance or lent equipment to local firefighters⁵⁹.
- **Training:** beyond interventions, each party can help the others by sharing their own expertise. CERN trains the Geneva and Ain fire brigades in chemical and radiological risks and, in return, the local fire brigades train the CERN firefighters in their areas of expertise. The CERN Fire and Rescue service also takes on trainee firefighters. Training is the main benefit of this agreement.
- **Equipment sharing:** the agreement allows the parties to exchange and pool their equipment. This also applies to facilities. As CERN is a large, secure site, it sometimes makes its buildings available for training purposes⁶⁰. Numerous benefits are therefore derived from this agreement in terms of equipment, premises, sites, uniforms and expertise.

A collaboration agreement was also signed in 2015⁶¹ between CERN and the Geneva University Hospitals (HUG) to establish a mobile emergency and resuscitation unit (SMUR) at CERN designed to respond to emergencies throughout CERN and the Canton of Geneva, to optimise the handling of medical emergencies throughout the CERN site and to provide ongoing rescue training for members of the CERN personnel (Medical Service and Fire and Rescue service). This agreement is renewed every five years. The benefits are similar to those set out above.

The CERN safety services team is made up of 60 people, including 48 firefighters, 10 of whom are on duty 24/7. The furthest point from CERN is Point 5 of the LHC (P5), where the CMS experiment is located. Two firefighters are permanently on duty there.

A strategy for the organisation and sharing of emergency services between CERN and the Host States has yet to be defined for the FCC. Its coverage will include the Haute-Savoie department.

5.5.2. Synergies with the emergency services

⁵⁸ <https://www.admin.ch/gov/fr/accueil/documentation/communiqués.msg-id-64867.html>

CERN firefighters are often called to Geneva airport to deal with radiation protection issues. Moreover, the people operating CERN's infrastructure in the control room are in constant communication with the local emergency services. This agreement has a significant impact that extends beyond the local area, with interventions carried out in Lyon and Lucerne, for example.

⁶⁰ This was the case for a training course on interventions in underground complexes, where the Geneva fire brigade was able to train in a CERN building.

⁶¹ <https://hse.cern/fr/content/convention-cern-hug>

The Haute-Savoie Departmental Fire and Rescue Service (SDIS 74)⁶² is a departmental public body made up of professional firefighters, volunteer firefighters and administrative, technical and specialist staff. It manages the emergency services in Haute-Savoie. The maps in annex 8.22 show all the emergency services in the vicinity of each site. Each site is within a 15-minute drive of a centre. Figure 13 shows the location of all safety and emergency services (hospital or clinic, fire and rescue, police) present on the territory of the FCC.

Synergy between the emergency services of the Host States and CERN could take the form of firefighter training: CERN would provide training at the fire and rescue centres located near each site to enable firefighters there to respond to emergencies at CERN and in the vicinity of the FCC. The equipment required would be supplied in part by CERN. CERN would play a role in organising further training, which would also help to better integrate the different rescue services in France and Switzerland.

⁶² Only the Department of Haute-Savoie is mentioned because the Department of Ain is already covered by the existing collaboration agreements.

08/03/2024

- | | |
|---------------------------------|------------------------------|
| Security and emergency services | Design |
| Hôpital ou clinique | PA31-4.0 |
| Incendie et secours | World Imagery |
| Police | World Imagery |
| Surface Point | Low Resolution 15m Imagery |
| PA31-4.0 | High Resolution 60cm Imagery |
| | High Resolution 30cm Imagery |

Citations

1:332,483

0 2 4 8 mi

0 3 6 12 km

Earthstar Geographics, Map data © OpenStreetMap contributors, Microsoft, Facebook, Inc. and its affiliates, Esri Community Maps contributors, Map layer by Esri, Multiple sources - Processed for CERN

Figure 13: Location of emergency and safety services present in the area covered by the FCC. Source: CERN.

5.6. LINKS WITH COMPANIES

The region's economy, particularly in Haute-Savoie, is based on several key sectors: tourism, agriculture and manufacturing. The Arve Valley, which stretches from the Mont Blanc massif to Bonneville, is a major industrial area in the region (see annex 8.23). It is renowned for its precision engineering, plastics and metallurgy industries. There may be certain synergies between these industries and the construction and maintenance of a machine like the FCC. The potential synergies between companies and the project are as follows:

- Educational programmes for students, which could be created in collaboration with companies (see the section on education and training).
- Collaboration in a range of subject areas with potential for development.
- The creation of a new business incubator to support the development of new companies and start-ups in the field of technology and innovation. This could be linked to the specialist areas of local businesses. InnoGEX, for example, is a CERN-accredited incubator whose mission is to stimulate the emergence and growth of innovative companies, with links to CERN technologies, in the Pays de Gex region.⁶³
- The use of the tools and skills of CERN scientists through programmes such as IDEFICS⁶⁴ (see the section “Sharing digital infrastructure”).

As an international scientific organisation, CERN must follow open procurement practices. Contracts cannot therefore be reserved exclusively for local companies.

5.7. OTHER SYNERGIES

5.7.1. Development of agriculture and forestry

A number of approaches can be employed to offset the use of agricultural land for the proposed FCC surface sites, including the implementation of collective agricultural compensation measures. An agricultural study will be carried out for this purpose.

In the plans for the reuse of material excavated in the local area, the aim is to develop synergies with agriculture and reforestation in order to improve the quality of forests, facilitate farming and mitigate the effects of climate change.

5.7.2. Sharing digital infrastructure

The institutional and research worlds have a wealth of experience in processing high-precision data. This expertise can be transferred to other areas. For example, the IDEFICS⁶⁵ (Informatics, data and companies for training and innovation in scientific computing and for society) project at the Annecy Laboratory for Particle Physics (LAPP) aims to create a bridge between regional companies and the LAPP via its MUST digital platform. This initiative, supported by the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), seeks to support local businesses in their digital transition, particularly in response to current challenges such as those posed by artificial intelligence and big data. By providing appropriate material resources, sharing knowledge and promoting applied research, IDEFICS aims to create an ecosystem in which institutional scientific innovation can be used to meet the concrete needs of local businesses. This partnership gives businesses access to advanced technical expertise and high-quality digital infrastructure, enabling them to grow and compete in an ever-changing economic environment. It provides an opportunity to share the computing and even storage power of digital platforms for the benefit of regional businesses.

⁶³ <https://www.innogex.fr/fr/>

⁶⁴ <https://idefics.fr/a-propos/>

⁶⁵ <https://idefics.fr/avec-idefics-le-lapp-souvre-aux-entreprises/>

5.7.3. Sharing data on the region

The FCC Feasibility Study will enable a wide range of data on the local area to be collected and analysed. This data must be freely accessible, in accordance with the H2020 grant agreement. Data on the environment, heat consumption, geodesy and other subjects will therefore be public and reusable.

6. SUMMARY

6.1. SYNERGIES

Table 19: Synergy potential for each site. Table 19 below shows the synergy potential for each site.

Green means that the elements present in this location have a high potential for synergies with the FCC project. **Orange** means that the elements present in this location have a moderate potential for synergies with the FCC project. This does not mean that there are no synergies, but that they are less significant than those shown in green.

Red means that there are no elements present in this location, resulting in a weak potential for synergies with the FCC project.

Table 19: Synergy potential for each site.

	PA	PB	PD	PF	PG	PH	PJ	PL
Heat recovery	Green	Green	Green	Green	Orange	Red	Orange	Orange
Reuse and distribution of water	Green	Green	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange	Green	Orange
Reinforcement of the electricity network	Orange	Orange	Green	Red	Green	Red	Green	Green
Sustainable tourism	Green	Red	Green	Orange	Green	Red	Green	Red
Local services	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Orange	Green	Green
Mobility	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Orange	Orange
Education and training	Green	Green	Green	Orange	Green	Red	Green	Red
Emergency services	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green

The following sections contain maps showing the opportunities available at each site. Some of those opportunities, including potential consumers of recovered waste heat, electricity networks and water distribution networks, could not be included on the maps. The maps should therefore not be used as the sole reference for opportunities.

6.2. OVERVIEW OF OPPORTUNITIES AT SITE PA

Figure 14: Overview of opportunities at site PA. Source: macarte.ign.fr.

6.3. OVERVIEW OF OPPORTUNITIES AT SITE PB

Figure 15: Overview of opportunities at site PB. Source: macarte.ign.fr.

6.4. OVERVIEW OF OPPORTUNITIES AT SITE PD

Figure 16: Overview of opportunities at site PD. Source: macarte.ign.fr.

6.5. OVERVIEW OF OPPORTUNITIES AT SITE PF

Figure 17: Overview of opportunities at site PF. Source: macarte.ign.fr.

6.6. OVERVIEW OF OPPORTUNITIES AT SITE PG

Figure 18: Overview of opportunities at site PG. Source: macarte.ign.fr.

6.7. OVERVIEW OF OPPORTUNITIES AT SITE PH

Figure 19: Overview of opportunities at site PH. Source: macarte.ign.fr.

6.8. OVERVIEW OF OPPORTUNITIES AT SITE PJ

Figure 20: Overview of opportunities at site PJ. Source: macarte.ign.fr.

6.9. OVERVIEW OF OPPORTUNITIES AT SITE PL

Figure 21: Overview of opportunities at site PL. Source: macarte.ign.fr.

7. CONCLUSION

This document is only an initial, preliminary analysis of the regional opportunities associated with the FCC site. The possibilities are numerous and must be further developed, either by the Host States in cooperation with CERN or as a follow-up to the preliminary technical studies carried out and made available by CERN.

Generally, the synergies identified at the scientific sites offer greater potential than those at the technical sites. The most difficult site to develop at present is site PH (Cercier/Marlioz), owing to its very rural location. However, projects could be developed there within the next 20 years.

This document identifies the main potential synergies and can be used as a starting point to develop some areas in greater detail.

To ensure the successful integration of the FCC in the region, these synergies must be developed in a harmonious and balanced way, taking into account local lifestyles, limiting the environmental impact and working with a range of local stakeholders. It will take several years to plan and implement the measures presented, and it will be necessary to establish strong national, regional and departmental foundations. To take full advantage of the FCC in the region, analyses and planning should therefore be initiated as soon as possible.

8. ANNEXES

8.1. HEAT RECOVERY NETWORK AT LHC POINT 8

The heat recovery network in Ferney-Voltaire recovers waste heat from Point 8 of the LHC. This heat is then distributed via a network of underground pipes to buildings in the town of Ferney-Voltaire for heating and cooling purposes. Once used, the cooled water is sent back to the power plant to be reheated, thereby creating a continuous cycle of heat distribution (see Figure 22)Figure 22: Operation of the heat recovery network at LHC P8 in Ferney-Voltaire.. Each year, 23 GWh of heat is distributed to the "Ferney-Genève Innovation" urban development zone and 20 GWh to the commune of Ferney-Voltaire. The waste heat is obtained at a very low price, enabling end consumers to pay less for their consumption (€77 incl. VAT/MWh)⁶⁶.

Figure 22: Operation of the heat recovery network at LHC P8 in Ferney-Voltaire. Source: Fédération des élus des entreprises publiques locales (Federation of elected representatives of local public companies).

⁶⁶ <https://www.lesepl.fr/trophees/reseau-danergie-pays-de-gex/>

8.2. BELLECOMBE/SCIENTRIER WASTE-WATER TREATMENT PLANT AND ANAEROBIC DIGESTION UNIT

QU'EST-CE QUE LA METHANISATION ?

La méthanisation permet l'élimination d'une quantité importante de matière organique en milieu anaérobie (fermé, donc sans rejet d'odeurs, et sans oxygène). Dans le cas de la station d'épuration de Bellecombe, la méthanisation permettra de produire un biogaz issu de la fermentation des boues produites par les effluents urbains (il n'y aura aucun autre apport de produit soit agricoles, déchets verts ou autres...). Le biogaz présente l'avantage d'être une énergie renouvelable, stockable et valorisable.

Actuellement, ce sont des boues, directement issues du traitement de l'eau usée, qui peuvent provoquer des nuisances olfactives. Avec l'extension, ces boues seront stockées dans un bâtiment désodorisé (filtres à charbon actif), puis injectées dans le méthaniseur par pompage. Les boues en sortie de méthaniseur auront déjà fermenté et seront stabilisées. La manipulation à l'air libre des boues digérées n'entraînera plus de nuisances et pas de reprise de fermentation.

Dans notre cas le biogaz sera épuré (filtré), et le méthane injecté directement dans le réseau GrDF) après traitement.

*Figure 23: Anaerobic digestion unit at the Bellecombe waste-water treatment plant, commissioned in 2022.
Source: Haute-Savoie.gouv.fr*

The anaerobic digestion unit must be kept at a temperature of 37 °C. The discussions under way with the waste-water treatment plant will enable the amount of heat required to be determined. The idea of using waste water for cooling purposes was also brought up during the discussions. A technical study on water quality is being carried out to determine the feasibility of this idea.

Figure 24: Operation of the anaerobic digestion unit. Source: Choisir.com.

8.3. FERME AQUAPONIQUE DU PAYS DE GEX

Aquaponics is a system in which waste produced by fish is used to feed plants. The nutrient-rich water is pumped to the plant beds, where the plants absorb the nutrients while filtering the water. The purified water is then sent back to the fish tanks, creating a closed, sustainable cycle (see Figure 25). This system facilitates efficient and ecologically responsible food production, as well as controlled water use (80 to 90% reduction in water use compared to normal market gardening). This system is not yet very well developed in France, owing, in large part, to the cost of electricity.

The greenhouses at the *Ferme Aquaponique du Pays de Gex* cover an area of approximately 1500 m² (see Figure 26 and Figure 27). The investment cost was €700 000. The electricity used to heat the greenhouses constitutes the greatest expense. Two to four tonnes of trout and 10 to 15 tonnes of seasonal fruit and vegetables are produced each year. The ideal year-round temperature is 20 °C for the greenhouses and 15 °C for the fish.

Figure 25: Operation of an aquaponic system. Source: Ferme Aquaponique du Pays de Gex.

Figure 26: Fruit and vegetables at the Ferme Aquaponique du Pays de Gex. Source: Author.

Figure 27: Trout pool at the Ferme Aquaponique du Pays de Gex. Source: Author.

8.4. HAUTE-SAVOIE EV CHARGING NETWORK

Figure 28: “Eborn” EV charging network on 10 February 2024. Source: eborn.

8.5. PLANT FOR WASHING REUSABLE PACKAGING

The reusable packaging system works by encouraging consumers to return their empty packaging to designated collection points. In exchange, they receive a partial or total refund of the amount paid at the time of purchase. The packaging is then sent to washing facilities where it is washed, disinfected and prepared for reuse. In France, this system is widely used for glass bottles, such as soft drinks bottles or wine bottles, as well for some plastic bottles, such as plastic water bottles. This reusable packaging helps to reduce waste and encourages the reuse of materials, which is beneficial for the environment. The companies TerraCycle, Loop⁶⁷, Reconcil⁶⁸ and RéseauConsignes⁶⁹ follow this principle. The temperature of the washing plants varies between 60 and 80 °C.

⁶⁷ <https://exploreloop.com/fr/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.reconcil.fr/>

⁶⁹ <https://zerowasteswitzerland.ch/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Projet-Reseau-Consignes-pour-SR-3.pdf>

8.6. PRINCIPLE OF HYDROPONICS IN VERTICAL AGRICULTURE

In vertical hydroponics, plants grow without sunlight with their roots immersed in a nutrient solution. In this system, plants are grown vertically using special structures such as towers or columns, making efficient use of space. A solution containing all the essential nutrients is pumped from a reservoir to the plant roots, thus ensuring optimal growth. This system enables efficient cultivation in urban settings, where ground space is limited (see Figure 29 Figure 29: Example of vertical agriculture. Source: Edengreen.).

Figure 29: Example of vertical agriculture. Source: Edengreen.

8.7. LOWLINE LAB PROJECT

Lowline Lab in New York City is an initiative to transform an old, abandoned tunnel into an innovative public space. The aim of this pilot project, which was launched in 2015, is to study the use of solar lighting technology to create an underground plant environment. Using solar tubes, sunlight is captured above ground and directed into the underground space, encouraging plant growth. As well as serving as a research laboratory, Lowline Lab organises educational visits and community programmes to teach the public about urban design, technological innovation and environmental sustainability. This initiative shows how abandoned underground spaces can be reused in a creative way to provide new public spaces, while exploring solutions to optimise the use of natural resources (see Figure 30: Photos of Lowline Lab in New York. Source: Lowline Lab.).

Figure 30: Photos of Lowline Lab in New York. Source: Lowline Lab.

8.8. SAMPLE ITINERARY OF A SCHOOL GROUP VISITING CERN AND THE SURROUNDING AREA

Table 20 shows a sample tourist itinerary consisting of over 200 km of travel, mainly on the Swiss side of Lake Geneva (see Figure 31). Source: Itinerary on Google Maps.).

Table 20: Sample school group itinerary.

Day 1	Visit to the city of Geneva
Day 2	CERN Science Gateway, S'Cool Lab - Meyrin
Day 3	CERN Control Centre, AMS, CMS – Prévessin – Cessy
Day 4	UN and International Red Cross and Red Crescent Museum – Geneva
Day 5	Olympic Museum – Lausanne, Chaplin's World – Vevey
Day 6	Roman ruins – Orbe, UEFA – Nyon
Day 7	Maison Cailler, HR Giger Museum – Gruyères, Mountain Studios – Montreux, Castle visit – Chillon

Figure 31: Sample school group itinerary. Source: Itinerary on Google Maps.

8.9. "VELO ET FROMAGE" (CYCLING AND CHEESE) ROUTES

The *Assemblée des départements de France* (Assembly of the Departments of France), CNIEL (French Dairy Interbranch Organisation), *Tourisme & Territoires* (French network of departmental agencies for tourism) and *Vélo & Territoires* (French network of local authorities to promote cycling) have put together a project called "*Vélo et fromages, à la découverte des Départements*" (Cycling and Cheese: Discovering the Departments) to promote these two positive and unifying trends. This concept consists of thematic cycle routes that showcase France's rich cheese-making heritage. Through the *Vélo & Fromages* project, visits to farms, cheese-making facilities and cheese-ripening cellars are integrated into existing cycle routes, giving cyclists the opportunity to discover the expertise of passionate craftspeople and the diverse culinary heritage of the different departments. The aim of this initiative is to present the activities being carried out in the departments in a variety of areas, such as tourism, cycling policies, sustainable development, rural life and digital technology. Three cycle routes in Haute-Savoie were awarded the "*Vélo et fromages*" label in 2020 (see Figure 32). While these routes may be difficult for beginners, it is possible to complete the journey in several stages and to use electric bicycles.

Vélo & FROMAGES
LA HAUTE-SAVOIE
SUR UN PLATEAU

3 itinéraires cyclables sur un plateau

Alliez plaisirs de l'exercice et de la table en explorant à vélo 3 itinéraires et leurs étapes fromagères, labellisés Vélo et Fromages.

Le Département vous invite à enfourcher votre bicyclette pour un circuit autour des Glières, en Vallée Verte ou autour du Semnoz, ponctué de visites de fermes, de caves d'affinage ou encore de marchés locaux et de points de vente.

À la clé : une découverte gourmande de notre patrimoine fromager.

Ces itinéraires ont été conçus avec l'Association des Fromages Traditionnels des Alpes Savoyardes (AFTA), fédérant les acteurs des filières des 8 Fromages de Savoie AOP et IGP.

Tour de la Vallée Verte
66 km > 950m D+

Tour des Glières
90 km > 1280m D+

Tour du Semnoz
55 km > 650m D+

haute savoie
le Département

Annecy

À retrouver sur experience.hautesavoie.fr
et son appli mobile **Haute-SavoieExperience**

Figure 32: "Vélo et fromages" routes Source: Haute-Savoie.

8.10. VIARHONA CYCLE ROUTE

Figure 33: ViaRhôna route. Source: Abicyclette Voyages.

8.11. CATERING AND ACCOMMODATION OPTIONS AT EACH SITE

The map of site PA is not shown here because the existing Meyrin and Prévessin sites – and their catering and accommodation facilities – are within 10 minutes’ drive of site PA. There are also a large number of restaurants and hotels in the areas, in Ferney-Voltaire, Prévessin-Moëns, Saint-Genis-Pouilly, Meyrin and Grand-Saconnex.

Figure 34: Local services within 10 minutes’ drive of site PB. Source: Author.

Figure 35: Local services within 10 minutes' drive of site PD. Source: Author.

Figure 36: Local services within 10 minutes' drive of site PF. Source: Author.

Figure 37: Local services within 10 minutes' drive of site PG. Source: Author.

Figure 38: Local services within 10 minutes' drive of site PH. Source: Author.

Figure 39: Local services within 10 minutes' drive of site PJ. Source: Author.

Figure 40: Local services within 10 minutes' drive of site PL. Source: Author.

8.12. TRAVELLING DISTANCES BETWEEN EACH SITE IN MINUTES AND KILOMETRES

Green: up to 29 minutes

Orange: between 30 and 40 minutes

Red: more than 40 minutes

The distances in minutes can vary considerably depending on road traffic conditions.

Table 21: Distances between each site by car in minutes and km.

	CERN Meyr.	CERN Prév.	PA	PB	PD	PF	PG	PH	PJ	PL
CERN Meyr.	0	4.0 km 7 min	4.6 km 10 min	17.1 km 40 min	37.3 km 32 min	49.0 km 40 min	39.9 km 40 min	35.3 km 35 min	29.3 km 27 min	13.2 km 12 min
CERN Prév.	4.0 km 7 min	0	3.6 km 5 min	21.5 km 35 min	40.9 km 35 min	52.2 km 41 min	43.5 km 41 min	38.6 km 36 min	30.3 km 26 min	14.2 km 13 min
PA	4.6 km 10 min	3.6 km 5 min	0	18.6 km 40 min	38.0 km 34 min	49.3 km 40 min	40.6 km 43 min	35.8 km 40 min	34.2 km 35 min	18.2 km 21 min
PB	17.1 km 40 min	21.5 km 35 min	18.6 km 40 min	0	14.6 km 18 min	26.2 km 27 min	39.8 km 38 min	37.9 km 37 min	34.4 km 36 min	32.5 km 45 min
PD	37.3 km 32 min	40.9 km 35 min	38.0 km 34 min	14.6 km 18 min	0	14.5 km 12 min	28.2 km 24 min	40.3 km 31 min	38.4 km 34 min	41.2 km 42 min
PF	49.0 km 40 min	52.2 km 41 min	49.3 km 40 min	26.2 km 27 min	14.5 km 12 min	0	13.2 km 12 min	35.6 km 30 min	50.1 km 41 min	52.7 km 47 min
PG	39.9 km 40 min	43.5 km 41 min	40.6 km 43 min	39.8 km 38 min	28.2 km 24 min	13.2 km 12 min	0	17.7 km 22 min	41.3 km 39 min	43.9 km 45 min
PH	35.3 km 35 min	38.6 km 36 min	35.8 km 40 min	37.9 km 37 min	40.3 km 31 min	35.6 km 30 min	17.7 km 22 min	0	15.2 km 21 min	38 km 45 min
PJ	29.3 km 27 min	30.3 km 26 min	34.2 km 35 min	34.4 km 36 min	38.4 km 34 min	50.1 km 41 min	41.3 km 39 min	15.2 km 21 min	0	21.1 km 20 min
PL	13.2 km 12 min	14.2 km 13 min	18.2 km 21 min	32.5 km 45 min	41.2 km 42 min	52.7 km 47 min	43.9 km 45 min	38 km 45 min	21.1 km 20 min	0

8.13. MAP OF THE LEMAN EXPRESS

Figure 41: Léman Express rail network. Source: TPG.

8.14. MAP OF THE PARTIALLY DISUSED PIED DU JURA RAILWAY LINE

Figure 42: Development potential of the Pied du Jura railway line. Source: Wikipedia.

8.15. TPG BUS NETWORK

Figure 43: Entire TPG network, sites PA, PB, PD, PJ and PL. Source: TPG.

8.16. PROXIM'ITI BUS NETWORK

Figure 44: Entire Proxim'iti network, sites PD and PF. Source: Proxim'iti

8.17. SIBRA BUS NETWORK

Figure 45: Entire Sibra network, site PG. Source: Sibra.

8.18. MINIMUM TRAVELLING DISTANCES BETWEEN EACH SITE BY PUBLIC TRANSPORT IN MINUTES

The routes take into account the public transport stops closest to the sites; some sites are more than 2 km away from a stop. "+ X min" represents the time from the stop to the site by car. **Waiting times and public transport timetables are not taken into account, meaning that the journeys will in reality take longer than the time stated (at least 15 minutes longer, as almost all routes involve changing buses).**

N/A = not applicable

Green: up to 30 minutes

Orange: up to 1 hour

Red: more than 1 hour

The distances in minutes can vary considerably depending on the state of road traffic and the transport network concerned.

Table 22: Minimum distances between each site by public transport in minutes.

	CERN Meyr.	CERN Prév.	PA	PB	PD	PF	PG	PH	PJ	PL
CERN Meyr.	0	0 h 19	0 h 20	0 h 54	1 h 22	1 h 13 + 6 min	1 h 45 + 5 min	n.a.	1 h 12 + 4 min	0 h 27
CERN Prév.	0 h 19	0	0 h 30	1 h 17	1 h 45	1 h 27 + 6 min	2 h 17 + 5 min	n.a.	1 h 14 + 4 min	0 h 46
PA	0 h 20	0 h 30	0	1 h 14	1 h 24	1 h 5 + 6 min	1 h 41 + 5 min	n.a.	1 h 07 + 4 min	0 h 28
PB	0 h 54	1 h 17	1 h 14	0	1 h 03	0 h 40 + 6 min	1 h 33 + 5 min	n.a.	0 h 48 + 4 min	1 h 03
PD	1 h 22	1 h 45	1 h 24	1 h 03	0	0 h 30 + 6 min	1 h 07 + 5 min	n.a.	0 h 55 + 4 min	1 h 27
PF	1 h 13 + 6 min	1 h 27 + 6 min	1 h 05 + 6 min	0 h 40 + 6 min	0 h 30 + 6 min	0	0 h 28 + 11 min	n.a.	0 h 48 + 10 min	1 h 16 + 6 min
PG	1 h 45 + 5 min	2 h 17 + 5 min	1 h 41 + 5 min	1 h 33 + 5 min	1 h 07 + 5 min	0 h 28 + 11 min	0	n.a.	1 h 12 + 6 min	1 h 38 + 2 min
PH	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
PJ	1 h 12 + 4 min	1 h 14 + 4 min	1 h 07 + 4 min	0 h 48 + 4 min	0 h 55 + 4 min	0 h 48 + 10 min	1 h 12 + 6 min	n.a.	0	1 h 12 + 4 min
PL	0 h 27	0 h 46	0 h 28	1 h 03	1 h 27	1 h 16 + 6 min	1 h 38 + 2 min	n.a.	1 h 12 + 4 min	0

8.19. UNIVERSITIES OF APPLIED SCIENCES AND TEACHER TRAINING COLLEGES IN SWITZERLAND

Situation et taille des hautes écoles spécialisées en Suisse, en 2022/23

Figure 46: Universities of applied sciences in Switzerland. Source: Swiss Federal Statistical Office.

Situation et taille des hautes écoles pédagogiques en Suisse, en 2022/23

Répartition des étudiants selon le sexe

- Femme (CH: 16 274)
- Homme (CH: 6 361)
- Canton avec une haute école pédagogique

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Eidgenössisches Departement des Innern EDI
Département fédéral de l'intérieur DFI
Bundesamt für Statistik BFS
Office fédéral de la statistique OFS

Source: OFS – Étudiants et examens finis des hautes écoles suisses
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Figure 47: Teacher training colleges in Switzerland. Source: Swiss Federal Statistical Office.

8.20. DEMARCHE GRAND CHANTIER TELT

The new Turin–Lyon transalpine rail link is a 270-km-long mixed (freight and passenger) railway line linking France and Italy.

Tunnel Euralpin Lyon Turin (TELT) is the binational public promoter in charge of the construction and operation of the cross-border section of the mixed rail line.

To support this large-scale project, *Démarche Grand Chantier*⁷⁰ – a special strategy for the preparation and coordination of large-scale construction projects – has been put in place.

Démarche Grand Chantier, which was launched by the French State in 2003, is designed to **support this unique project** before, during and after the construction work and to ensure its **successful integration into the local region**.

The Prefect of Savoie is responsible for ensuring the implementation of this strategy, which was adopted in a regional agreement.

This agreement – the *Contrat de territoire Maurienne* – unites the State, the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region, the Department of Savoie, the *Syndicat du Pays de Maurienne* (intercommunal local authority for Pays de Maurienne), the local authorities in the Maurienne valley and the TELT around a project that presents three key areas of opportunity: the presence of the construction site in the region, the economic support for the region that will be generated as a result of it and the prospect of an improved European rail service by 2029. Funding worth €40.7 M was allocated between 2015 and 2020 and an observatory was created.

Progress after three years:

Coordination of the construction site

Lyon–Turin: 3rd largest employer in the Maurienne region

Developing education and training:

- *Mon emploi Lyon–Turin*: a service to help people find jobs on the construction site or complete training and to recruit the future Lyon–Turin employees.

Supporting the local economy:

- Support platform for the local and regional economy: a service to facilitate access to worksites for local and regional companies or to develop services for employees.
- Renovation of the public housing stock of OPAC Savoie.

Regional development

Research and development:

- Support for the development of the Modane Underground Laboratory run by Université Grenoble Alpes.
- A future centre of expertise on tunnels in Maurienne.

Energy transition:

- Creation of a wood-fired heating plant in Saint-Julien-Mont-Denis and a wood shed for the Modane heating plant.
- Thermal renovation of several public buildings.

Environment:

- Creation of more than 160 km of cycle routes.
- First bike festival.

Housing:

- Renovated accommodation for Lyon–Turin employees.

⁷⁰ <https://www.telt.eu/fr/demarche-grand-chantier-lyon-turin/>

- 50 homes renovated already in Saint-Jean-de-Maurienne.

Development:

- Renovation of Joseph Gavarini stadium in Saint-Jean-de-Maurienne, a major sports facility.
- The areas around the stations in Saint-Arve and Modane (currently under study) will be redeveloped to make them more accessible and practical.
- A dozen town centre regeneration projects have been launched to revitalise towns and improve quality of life.

8.21. MAP OF SCHOOLS AND COLLEGES

Figure 48: Map of French schools and colleges. Source: Géoportail.

Figure 49: Map showing the number of schools in the canton of Geneva. Source: Swiss Federal Statistical Office.

8.22. LOCATION OF THE EMERGENCY SERVICES FOR EACH SITE

Site PA – Ferney-Voltaire

Since CERN is 10 minutes' drive from site PA, CERN firefighters can go there directly.

Site PB – Presinge/Choulex

CERN already has an agreement with Switzerland on mutual assistance between the emergency services.

Site PD – Nangy

Figure 50: Emergency services at site PD. Source: Author.

- Arthaz-Pont-Notre-Dame first response centre
Division: *Groupement du Genevois* (Group of French communes bordering the Canton of Geneva)
Number of personnel: 10 volunteer firefighters
8 min
- Arenthon first response centre
Division: *Groupement du Genevois* (Group of French communes bordering the Canton of Geneva)
Number of personnel: 11 volunteer firefighters

9 min

- *Centre Hospitalier Alpes-Léman (CHAL)* in Contamine-sur-Arve
Number of personnel: 2500 members of staff/700 beds
In the immediate vicinity

Site PF – Eteaux/La Roche-sur-Foron

Figure 51: Emergency services at site PF. Source: Author.

- Pays Rochois fire station in Etaux
Division: *Groupement du Genevois* (Group of French communes bordering the Canton of Geneva)
Number of personnel: 12 professional firefighters and 56 volunteer firefighters
3 min
- Arenthon first response centre
Division: *Groupement du Genevois* (Group of French communes bordering the Canton of Geneva)
Number of personnel: 11 volunteer firefighters
8 min

The nearest emergency hospital is the CHAL in Contamine-sur-Arve.

Site PG – Charvonnex/Groisy

Figure 52: Emergency services at site PG. Source: Author.

- Thorens-Groisy fire station
Division: *Groupement du bassin Annécien* (Annecy area group)
Number of personnel: four professional firefighters and 46 volunteer firefighters
2 min
- *Centre Hospitalier Annecy Genevois*
Number of personnel: 4700 members of staff/1300 beds
12 min

Site PH – Cercier/Marlioz

Figure 53: Emergency services at site PH. Source: Author.

- Cruseilles fire station
Division: *Groupement du bassin Annécien* (Annecy area group)
Number of personnel: four professional firefighters and 51 volunteer firefighters
14 min
- Frangy fire station
Division: *Groupement du bassin Annécien* (Annecy area group)
Number of personnel: three professional firefighters and 34 volunteer firefighters
11 min
- Chilly-Menthonnex first response centre
Division: *Groupement du bassin Annécien* (Annecy area group)
Number of personnel: 18 volunteer firefighters
13 min
- Sillingy first response centre

Division: *Groupement du bassin Annécien* (Annecy area group)

Number of personnel: 33 volunteer firefighters

11 min

- *Centre Hospitalier Annecy Genevois*

Number of personnel: 4700 members of staff/1300 beds

18 min

Site PJ – Dingy-en-Vuache/Vulbens

Figure 54: Emergency services at site PD. Source: Author.

- Vulbens first response centre

Division: *Groupement du Genevois* (Group of French communes bordering the Canton of Geneva)

Number of personnel: 26 volunteer firefighters

3 min

- *Centre Hospitalier Annecy Genevois* at Saint-Julien-en-Genevois

Number of personnel: 4700 members of staff/1300 beds
18 min

Site PL – Challex

Site PL is located close to CERN (around 10 minutes' drive away) and can therefore benefit from the existing collaboration agreements.

8.23. ECONOMIC ACTIVITY ZONES IN THE AREA COVERED BY THE FCC AND AT THE START OF THE ARVE VALLEY

Figure 55: Main economic activity zones. Source: Simplanter.fr.